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ACCOUNTABILITY MODEL FOR MANAGEMENT OF AUTONOMY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Higher Education Institutions cherish the desire to obtain the status of 'Autonomy'. This gives substantial freedom and manoeuvrability to improve the quality of education and global brand building exercise which is crucial for their survival and growth in the face of challenges and competitions. Autonomy implies the freedom to have self-sustainable practices in the overall management of academic and administrative matters. Developing new courses, designing curriculum, determining fee structure, admission of students, engaging teachers, remuneration and retention, teaching-learning, examination and evaluation, and grading, all come under the purview of autonomy. Eventually, autonomy is paving way for increased responsibility and accountability. This paper aims to discuss the institutional responsibility-autonomy linkages in the main operational areas of autonomy and illustrates the accountability outcomes of autonomy. Attempt is also made to arrive at an Accountability Management model which compare conventional management practice styles and Accountability Management practice styles and discusses the processes which come into play therein.

Keywords : Autonomy, Accountability Management, Higher Education Institutions

1. INTRODUCTION:

Autonomy is considered as an essential feature for the sustainable growth of higher education institutions in developed countries. Devoid of political and bureaucratic control, autonomy helps institutions to improve their systems and practices to enhance quality standards, thereby contributing to society. Autonomy helps institutions to think independently with responsibility and generate accountability. Such thinking is considered as 'thinking from the top'. On the other hand, in many countries, higher education is controlled by corrupt politics and bureaucracy and hence they cannot think independently. Institutions which cannot think with responsibility and accountability to further their growth are considered as 'thinking from the bottom'. Such institutions remain stunted chained by regulations of accreditation organizations. Autonomy implies the freedom to have self-sustainable practices in the overall management of academic and administrative matters. Developing new courses, designing curriculum, determining fee structure, admitting students, engaging teachers, remuneration and retention, teaching-learning, examination and evaluation, and grading, all come under the purview of autonomy. Eventually, autonomy is paving way for increased responsibility and accountability [1-13].

2. OBJECTIVES AND AGENDA :

The paper is conceptual in nature and the following objectives are set:

- (1) To know the implications of autonomy for higher education institutions
- (2) To relate autonomy with institutional accountability
- (3) To identify responsibility – accountability linkages
- (4) To determine the accountability outcomes of autonomy in HEIs
- (5) To distinguish conventional management and accountability management

3. RESPONSIBILITY-ACCOUNTABILITY LINKAGES :

Starting from designing curriculum to admitting students, teaching-learning, examination, evaluation, and grading, covers the broad spectrum of institutional activities which benefits from autonomy and translates its responsible actions to ensure accountability. Eight major areas of autonomy identified and discussed here reveal the responsibility-accountability relationship on the institutional side. For instance, it is well within the responsibility invested in the institutions having the autonomy to choose courses which they should offer. Conventional multipurpose courses now serve no use such that institutions should respond to changing times and evolving context of job markets. Business Analytics, E-Commerce, Supply Chain Management, etc. are some such examples of evolving interdisciplinary areas. While at the same time, it shall be binding to ensure that the students who take up such courses are employable and secure employment. Another aspect is designing a curriculum where it is well within the manoeuvrability of institutions to make it student-centric. This would ensure adequate development of knowledge and skills of the students. Coming to admissions to various programmes, the institution should ensure merit as decisive to preserve equal opportunity to all prospective students. Fee is a sensitive issue because it is the financial backbone of the institution. Very high fee structure can prevent genuine students losing opportunity, while very low will render unviable to operate or maintain quality. The responsibility in this regard would be deciding on a reasonable fee structure and obviously it demonstrates accountability very well [14-15].

Teachers are the instruments of the institution which would serve to display its accountability through the fulfilment of the goals of the institution. The goals would invariably include quality teaching to quality produces. The responsibility of hiring competent teachers thus becomes important. Remunerating and retaining such teachers call for equitable rewards which reflect the institution's accountability to maintain a contended and productive work force. In modern times partnership based learning has received great attention in higher education, where teaching and learning are mutually complementary. Students and teachers narrow their distance (physical and intellectual) and students actually become empowered to discover knowledge. Learning what they don't know is also discovering knowledge because the teacher then assumes the role of a facilitator. This cannot be attained in the conventional frame and needs to evolve innovations and best practices. Examination and evaluation put together is the true measure of student competence acquired through doing the course and it is the responsibility vested in the institutions to make it so. Foolproof examination and evaluation spells out the accountability of the institution for results that are a true measure of competency acquired. In the end, grading serves to indicate the accomplishment of students, and reflect the quality of the institution [16-17]. The institutional responsibility-accountability linkages shown in table 1.

Table 1: Institutional Responsibility and Accountability Linkages

Sl.No.	Area of Autonomy	Explicit Responsibility	Implicit Accountability
1.	Choice of Courses	Customised to industry relevance	Employability generation
2.	Designing Curriculum	Student centric in focus	Development of knowledge and skills
3.	Admission of Students	Merit as decisive	Ensure equality of opportunity
4.	Determining fee structure	Reasonable viable	Not deterrent to deserving
5.	Engaging Teachers	Depends on competence	Fulfilment of goals of institution
6.	Remuneration and Retention	Equitable rewards	Contentment for sustaining efficiency.
7.	Teaching and Learning	Innovations and Best practices	Partnership based learning
8.	Examination and Evaluation	True measure of competence	Commitment to results
9.	Grading	Projects accomplishments of students	Reflection of quality

4. ACCOUNTABILITY OUTCOMES OF AUTONOMY :

It is interesting to see the accountability dimensions in terms of institutional, teacher, and students against some of the prominent actions and its outcomes, in the major areas of autonomy. Taking for instance, autonomy to offer new courses will result in exploring new opportunities which suits the needs and interests of the prospective students as well as the demand factor in job market, existing body of knowledge already accumulated in the subject, influence of other institutions and even those of competitors. Similarly the autonomy for curriculum design and development affords plenty of freedom to customise as per need and relevance. Taking the two together it will create institutional accountability of filling knowledge gaps, a lasting pursuit for higher education institutions, as well as converting it student centric. Teachers are accountable through building desired competency among the learners as well as enhancing student learning. Students also display accountability by offering themselves willingly to take challenges opened up through the new courses and demonstrate increased involvement in learning. Accountability dimensions of nine major areas that can translate autonomy in action are listed in table 2.

Table 2 : Accountability Outcomes of Autonomy

Sl.No.	Autonomy in Action	Outcome	Institutional Accountability	Teacher Accountability	Student Accountability
1.	New Courses	Exploring opportunities	Filling knowledge gaps	Building desired competency	Willingness to undertake challenges

2.	Curriculum Development	Customization	Student centric focus	Enhance student learning	Increased involvement in learning
3.	Teaching-Learning Methodologies	Variety and diversity	Promoting innovation	Adopting Best practices	Developing Partnership
4.	Determining Fee Structure	Generating Revenue	Maintaining quality service	Best return for the students	Value for money
5.	Remuneration and Rewards	Fair Rewards	Rewards suited to serve as motivators	Expressing commitment	Respect for the profession
6.	Examination and Evaluation Reforms	True and Objective assessment	Ensure transparency	Best suited to student needs	Reverence and acknowledgement
7.	Faculty Performance Assessment	Merit as measure of performance	Nurture standards	Maintain consistency	Honest and objective
8.	Student Associations	Cultivate leadership	Practice democracy	Empowered students	Avoid misuse
9.	Grading	Translating assessment into score	True reflection of judged ability	Symbol of effort	Mark of success

5. CONVENTIONAL VS. ACCOUNTABILITY MANAGEMENT :

Conventional management and Accountability management is distinguished in Table 3. Seven major styles of practices in conventional management are listed and the corresponding styles in accountability management are presented. The start of an activity is assigning responsibility. In contrast, accountability management is more proactive, the individual owns to assume responsibility. If this condition is to be created a process has to be set in motion which gives greater and sufficient role clarity for the individual. Role clarity here is not about structured rules, structured relationships, and structured rules but of understanding and identifying himself as the performer. This evolves out of conceptualization of self where the individual looks inward rather than look outward to discover his role. Targets are set and given, rather imposed on the person usually in conventional management practice whereas in accountability management the person arrives at the target, a process involving role perception –how he looks at it – as friend or enemy. This boils down to looking at work (and target) as a friend or enemy, definitely a question of attitude. Consciousness of task enables to befriend the target. Individuals work as a team in executing a task and usually, teams are engaged. Accountability management believes that teamwork is inherent quality, but there needs to further teamwork through a process of role enrichment where the employee identifies his role as being shared by others and integrate himself into a team. This builds a bond which releases considerable synergy through collaborative action. Extracting work is most often what conventional management is all about. Every other activity is built around making it softer in appeal to the individual. Accountability management believes in creating (generating) work, something that is a conscious and willful action of the individual. This is set in place through a process of role actualization, a condition which is manifested by a philosophy of creative manifestation. In order to sustain and maintain

momentum, incentives are used as inducements. It could be material or non-material inducements.

Table 3 : Horizontal Vertical Matrix of Accountability Management

Conventional Management Practice styles	Accountability Management Practice styles	Processes	Principles
Assigning responsibility	Assuming responsibility	Role Clarity	Conceptualization of self
Fixing Target	Arriving at Target	Role Perception	Consciousness of Task
Engaging Teams	Promoting Teamwork	Role Enrichment	Synergise through collaboration
Extracting work	Generating performance	Role actualization	Creativity manifestation
Inducing incentives	Projecting models	Role modelling	Positive message
Subjecting to assessment	Jointly reviewing	Role matching	Collective reflection
Monitoring	Recycling	Role reactivation	Goal attainment

In accountability management projecting role models is initiated as a process throughout. These role models are the best performers. The idea is to lay a positive image to copy so that inhibitions or negative feelings are reduced. Performance is periodically assessed, a painful feeling for the individual is replaced by a joint review that leads to a process of role matching which is real learning. Such learning paves way for improvement. Here the philosophy adopted is a collective reflection, where no accusing finger is pointed. Lastly, there is monitoring which means keeping track of individual and his work. This is replaced with recycling where drawbacks are washed out through a process of reactivation. This is the point of attainment of the goal [18-20].

The sequencing in conventional management is vertically matched with sequencing in accountability management. The accountability management may be visualised both horizontally or vertically as depicted in the table. The individual is replaceable in an accountability management model with an institution. Here, for instance, autonomy refers to a new environment (conditions) to function for the organization and is synonymous to a new individual in a job situation. Autonomy release a host of issues which alter the work environment for an institution where it has enough choices to make by virtue of the extent of freedom vested in it. Hence involves adoption of management practices, of how an institution should be managed, just as how an individual should be managed.

6. CONCLUSION :

The present era of evolving organizational-institutional behavioural theories has thrown up new systems of management, the one that is suggested here namely Accountability Management. Accountability management is distinguishable from Conventional man management or Human

Resources Development Management. It presupposes that an urge for creativity exists in every individual and work is an expression of creativity. Individual loves work and likes works, where he is provided the opportunities to own a sense of belongingness with his work, assume responsibility instead of assign responsibility, arrive at target instead fixing targets, promoting teams instead of engaging teams, generating performances instead of extracting performances, projecting models instead of inducing incentives, jointly reviewing instead of subjecting to assessments, and role reactivation and recycling instead of monitoring. Overall the Accountability Management model is meant to build and manage accountability, not individual or his work. The model suggested here has great relevance because it is not limited to individuals in work situations, but also to organizations and institutions that function in a broader social environment where particularly there is scope for autonomy in operation.

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HOW TO LEARN RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT FROM SAPTAPADI - INDIAN MARRIAGE MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Relationship is important for an individual as well as to an organisation. Better relationships brings the people closer and strengthen the mutual concern and care. In a business organisation amicable relationship between employer and employee leads to its growth and development. This paper aims to highlight the relationship oath taken by bride and bridegroom in Hindu marriage and its relevance to business situations. Integrity mutual trust responsible behaviour, whole hearted participation would help the business organisation. It accelerates the organizations progress in a faster rate in the changing market environment.

Keywords : Hindu marriage, Seven combined steps, Conducive environment, Social welfare, Organisational stability.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Marriage is a religious sacrament. It enables the young bride and bridegroom to enter their married life in the presence of relatives, friends, and elders. It is perceived that the blessings of elders during marriage functions enable the young couples to nurture their future smoothly with everlasting bondage between them [1-3].

In Hindu marriages especially among Brahmins, both bride and groom take seven oaths in front of holy fire in seven steps. This is known as “Saptapadi”. The holy fire is the witness “Agni Sakshi” for the oaths taken by them. The responsibility of the priest who performs the marriage is not only to administer the oath but also explain to the bride and groom the meaning and implications of the oath and seven steps. For each step with oath, both the groom and bride have to go around the holy fire as per the guidance of the priest [4-7].

The Saptapadi oath covers role and responsibility of both the bride and groom in their entire married life. They not only accept each other in the presence of holy fire but also agree to maintain harmony, trust mutual concern and care towards property, family and live as responsible and respectful citizens in the community [8-9]. The lessons of Saptapadi oath can also be extended to the corporate world where employee-employer relationship prevails.

2. OBJECTIVES & MEHODOLOGY:

The objective of the paper is to explain the relevance of “saptapadi” (seven steps) oath taken by bride and groom during the **occasion** of their marriage and its implication to business world. The paper is based on the conceptual analysis of the contents of oath taken by bride and groom, administered by the priest and management of such relationship by committed couples.

3. SAPTAPADI STEPS & MEANINGS :

Saptapadi oath contains seven parts and is integrated with combined walk of seven steps to be performed by bride and groom. Each combined step has its own significance to manage future married life together.

Step One: “Om Esha Yekapadi Bavah”, means the oath taken in the first step is to nourish each other. It is a promise of both bride and groom to show their responsibility of taking care of others in the life journey. Both have equal responsibility. If husband is the bread earner the wife has to take care of household activities in a responsible way. There is no under estimation of the work of anyone. The responsibilities of both husband and wife are of equal importance, then only family can move in the right direction. Here complex of superiority or subordinations does not arise because both are responsible and need to perform their tasks in the family journey. This relationship between husband and wife and their role and responsibilities can be extended to corporate world where employees employer relationship prevails.

To nourish the organisation both the employer and employee need to play their role appropriately. Employer needs to extend his affection towards employees and the employees in turn needs to extend their loyalty and integrity towards their organisation where they earn their livelihood. Ego and hatredness spoils the environment and work culture. Mutual harmony and trustworthiness among both the party enable the organisation to accelerate its development process.

Step Two : “OM URJE DWIPAD BHAVAH” the oath in second step is the determination towards progress and growth. In the journey of family life there is need for growth and further improvement in terms of financial strength of the family and capacity of the family to sustain in vibrant conditions. Hence the role of both husband and wife is to put efforts to enhance the stability of the family and also determine to grow and improve the base of the family. Both need to aim at future progress.

In an organisational setup both employee and employer need to put their heart and soul towards the success of their business. There is need for complete effort and whole hearted participation of both the party to usher the development process. They need to work efficiently and effectively to build the image of the organisation and bring stability in its position.

Step Three : “OM RAJAS POSHAY TRIPADI BHAVAH” the third step in Saptapadi is pertaining to promise of both to preserve the wealth and property belonging to the family. The wealth or resources of the family should not be depleted or destroyed by the action of any one of them. To maintain standard of the family, preservation of family resource plays an important role. Husband and wife need to pay attention to preserve or conserve the family resources. This helps them to lead a good life and also to show the way of living to their next generation.

In business situation it is the responsibility of both owners and employees to maintain the resources for sustainability and growth of business enterprise. Their action or inaction should not come in the way of the resource depletion. We can see in several instances the revolutionary workers destroy the business resources. Both the party need to understand their responsibility to keep up the fitness of business.

Step Four : “Om Bhayobhayah Chatuspadi Bhavah” the fourth step is to serve each other with happiness and harmony. Providing needy service and care taking is the responsibility of both. While serving another person both of them need to perform their task happily with utmost care. Mutual understanding and clarity in purpose enable them to do their work joyfully with at most satisfaction. During ailment or sickness, the service of other person with affection and care is very much important then only both of them feel that they are integral part of family system with mutual binding relationship.

In the organisational climate it is the responsibility of both employees and employer to provide yeomen needy service during critical situation. Performing their task with at most care help the organisation to come out of crisis. There is no scope for showing vengeance or neglecting their work due to their prejudiced feeling. Both parties have to understand the problem of the organisation and need to pay attention to solve it whole heartedly.

Step Five : Om Praja Bhayah Panchapadi Bhavah” The fifth step is related to the promise of both to take care of their children. They need to stick to the principle nurse the baby and protect the child and provide required guidance and support until the children become adult.

In a business set up it is the responsibility of the top management and also the bottom-line staff to see that their products are processed, manufactured and delivered to the customers in an acceptable way.

Step Six : “Om Rutu Bhayah Saptapadi Bhavah” In the sixth step both the groom and bride take the oath to be together forever in all seasons, in all situations of stress and difficulties. Be together during the situations of problem improve their love and affection and it helps them to face challenges in life. Both of them determine to maintain oneness throughout their life. There is no question of backing out or not willing to give company in a distress situation. Unity gives the strength during unfavourable situations.

In a business activity boom and recession is common. Here both the top management and shop floor workers need to maintain unity among themselves to absorb the shock given by market situation.

Step Seven : “Om Esha Sakha Saptapadi Bhavah” The seventh and last step is pertaining to maintain ideal and everlasting friendship in thinking and acting. In physical relation (kaya) in interaction (Vacha) in thinking (manasa) they need to maintain purity as real friends. Both agree to maintain ideal relationship which will be an example to others. This brings happiness and harmony throughout their family life.

4. MANAGEMENT LESSON ANALYSIS & SUGGESTIONS :

Today in marriage functions everything is done like a ritual. Both bride and groom are not clear about the relevance of Saptapadi. Understanding the relevance is very much necessary because divorce and separation after marriage and misunderstanding is common nowadays. Understanding the principles laid behind Saptapadi and its moral implications enable both bride and groom to discharge their roles and responsibilities in the family life. The bondage between them has ethical and moral implications. This is the responsibility of the elders to educate the young people to be clear about their duties and responsibilities in the family life, lack of which may break the relationship and cause problems in their family life. While applying this concept to business environment, it is both the top management and employee are responsible for survival and growth of the business. Both of them are like two wheels of a cart. Both the wheels need to be perfect for the mobility of the cart. The cart cannot move smoothly if one wheel is strong enough and the other one is weak. Unity, integrity, honesty, loyalty, harmony and mutual relationship are the necessary concepts for bringing solid foundation for business.

5. CONCLUSION:

The concept of saptapadi is relevant for family life which helps to keep up better relationship among husband and wife. Maintenance of cordial relationship among people create a conclusive environment in a community. Quality of living calls for better understanding and mutual cooperation. Ideal family helps to create ideal society and social welfare. In business activity it is the relationship between the management and working class which decides the future of the business.

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MANAGEMENT OF UNIVERSAL TECHNOLOGIES & THEIR INDUSTRY IMPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

It is observed that certain technologies have grown and expanded their branches to many areas and sectors of practice in such a way that they have been designated as General-Purpose Technologies. Such general-purpose technologies are identified and used in many industries to do business and to solve or simplify the problems of industries. During the last few years, it is observed that out of many general-purpose technologies, two technologies have shown accelerated growth and gave birth to many underlying sub-technologies: (1) Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT), and (2) Nanotechnology (NT). These two technologies are further identified as “Universal Technologies” due to their potential capability of solving problems related to basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human beings in society. ICCT and Nanotechnology have opened up the possibility of ubiquitous solutions to many problems related to production and service industries by offering automated mobility, stability, and sustainability. In this paper, we have identified various strategies for effective management of ICCT & NT underlying technologies in solving issues pertaining to basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human beings in society. The paper also discusses how these universal technologies can be unified to further strengthen their abilities in redefining the productivity in production-related industries and performance in service-related industries with the objective of moving towards technological singularity by building super-intelligent self-replicating machines.

Keywords: Universal technologies, Technology management, ICCT, Nanotechnology, Technological singularity, Technological unification, Redefining productivity & performance.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Technology management is an area of Management Science where business organizations plan and implement their technology development and adoption strategy by means of predicting and foreseeing the future changes so that to create a technology roadmap for competition, sustainability, and growth & prosper. Technology management is a part of corporate strategic management and organizations should identify a suitable strategy to compete in its industry by adopting a suitable strategy. Strategic management is a branch of management which consists of various well-structured and implementable ideas to ensure success in any decision-making process of that management level. Strategic management usually consists of some short cut methods in the decision-making process of a manager to ensure winning. Strategic management principles can be applied at operations level, business level, corporate or industry levels. The strategies followed at the operational level of an organization to improve productivity or efficiency in production organization or service organizations respectively are called operational

strategy. Operational level strategies are also called functional strategies due to the reason that they are used in functional areas of the organizations. The various operational strategies include Design of Goods and Services, Quality Management, Process and Capacity Design, Location Strategy, Layout Design and Strategy, Human Resources and Job Design, Supply Chain Management, Inventory Management, etc. The strategies followed at the business level for new product or service innovations in production organization or service organization respectively is called business strategy. The various business strategies include Cost leadership, Aggressive marketing for enhancing sales, Product/service differentiation, Pricing strategy, and gaining technological advantages using emerging suitable technology. The strategies followed by an organization at corporate or industry level are called corporate strategy. These include growth strategy, expansion & diversification strategies, partnership strategies, Business stabilization strategies, Technology adoption strategies, Online business strategies, etc.

As well known in business management, management decision making is nothing but (1) identifying a issue as per the objective of the organization, (2) analysing the issue to discover the problems, (3) Synthesize the possible solutions or ideas for the problems, (4) Choose an optimum solutions using Quantitative analysis/operations research, (5) Implementing the optimum solution to get expected results as benefits. In this paper, the process of identification of emerging technologies based on analysing technologies using universal technology concept and the steps in adopting such technologies for realizing the organizational objectives of increasing productivity and/or enhancing performance.

Many scholarly published research works is reported in the areas like technology management, strategies to manage technology, universal technologies, redefining productivity & performance, and strategic management of technologies. The review of related publications obtained from google scholar search is listed in table 1.

2. OBJECTIVES:

The objective of this paper is to analyse and synthesize various strategies required to identify and monitor, adapt, and manage emerging technologies that can redefine the business processes for an organization. Following are the specific objectives identified and addressed:

- 1) To analyse the purview of Information Communication & Computation technology (ICCT) in solving the problems and supporting the advancement of civilization.
- 2) To analyse the purview of Nanotechnology in solving the problems and supporting the advancement of civilization.
- 3) To discuss how ICCT and Nanotechnologies work together as complementary and unified technologies.
- 4) To redefine the objectives of productivity of Manufacturing industries using unified universal technologies.
- 5) To redefine the objectives of the performance of Service industries using unified universal technologies.
- 6) To predict the technological singularity level of unified universal technologies through a technology roadmap.

3. Universal Technologies :

It is observed that some of the general purpose technologies are grown as umbrella technologies and gave birth to many sub technologies under them as underlying technologies to solve basic and advanced problems of the society to make the life of human being comfortable. These

underlying technologies are growing both horizontally and vertically to solve (1) basic problems like nutritious food, clean water for drinking and irrigation, low cost durable shelters, low cost, reliable and renewable energy for individuals, homes, transports, and industries, quality basic education for everybody, affordable health services; (2) advanced problems like easy & affordable access to products and services related to everyone's daily needs for easy & comfortable life with happiness; (3) dreamy desires related problems like flying, space travel, virtual reality, life span expansion, and much more fantasy including antiaging and achieving immortality. The technology which supports to solve the problems related to the above three areas are called universal technology. Thus, universal technologies either alone or with other general purpose technologies are capable of solving all kinds of problems in the society. Based on scanning the technologies of the 21st century, it is identified that two general purpose technologies have grown to support many underlying technologies and shown their capabilities to solve almost any problems in society at all the three levels. These two technologies identified as universal technologies are Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) [1-6] and Nanotechnology (NT) [7-9]. Both these universal technologies have many underlying technologies and these underlying technologies are also capable to grow as killer technology in their application areas.

3.1 ICCT Underlying Technologies :

Information Communication & Computation Technology (ICCT) is a Technology to generate, transmit, process, store, and deliver information in the electronic or optical signal format. Mainly of these are used for intangible applications in various industry sectors both for managing and controlling various processes.

- (1) Artificial Intelligence & Robotics
- (2) Big Data & Intelligence Technology
- (3) Blockchain Technology
- (4) Cloud Computing Technology
- (5) Cyber Security Technology
- (6) 3D Printing Technology
- (7) Digital Marketing Technology
- (8) Internet & Internet of Things (IOT)
- (9) Information Storage Technology
- (10) Optical Computing Technology
- (11) Online Education Technology
- (12) Virtual and Augmented Reality

Applications of ICCT underlying Technologies :

ICCT underlying technologies [31] are used for developing machines which can understand, plan, think, compare, and decide like human beings using artificial intelligence technology (AIT). They can also communicate, monitor, and control the devices interconnected using the internet of things technology (IoT). They can analyse and compare, and identify the intelligence for business using Big data & Intelligence technology. The machines can keep track of information or financial transactions which can completely eliminate fraud and corruption in the society using Blockchain technology. Human beings and machines can make use of distant hardware devices, software, and other applications without owning them and as rental facilities using cloud computing technology. The secrecy & security of the information stored, transmitted, and processed can be maintained using cyber security technology. As technology progress and

aspirations of people enhance, more and more data and information storage facilities are required and can be realized using information storage technology. Development of high speed computers are continuously in demand for integrating computational processes support the entire world using optical computers and cloud computing technologies so that few computers are enough to maintain world information processing requirement. Any device or structure made of any material or mix of materials in any size can be produced by three-dimensional printing layer by layer to produce real devices and systems using 3D Printing technology. The companies in any industry and individuals can sell their products and services to entire globe by means low cost, affordable marketing using the internet called digital marketing technology. ICCT also allows ubiquitous education & training systematically using online education technologies and models so that off-campus education in any area and at any level are possible. Virtual reality technology allows to create an artificial environment to mimic the real situations with the help of a computer machine and presented to a user in such a way that the user suspends the belief and accepts it as a real environment. Table 1 lists some of the prominent applications of ICCT underlying technologies in industries and for individuals in society.

Table 1 : Prominent applications of ICCT underlying technologies

S. No.	ICCT Underlying Technologies	Prominent Applications
1	Artificial Intelligence & Robotics	Creating intelligent machines which can understand, plan, think, compare, and decide like human beings. The objective is to create super intelligent machines which can mimic the actions of human brain and overtake human intelligence.
2	Big Data & Intelligence Technology	Continuous data generated at high speed from CCD's and business processes are analysed by means of descriptive analytics, predictive analytics, and prescriptive analytics to find intelligence and relationship associated with them for futuristic decisions.
3	Blockchain Technology	Protects the information or documents related to a chain of transactions so that all and every previous transaction related to a digital document or digital currency so that any kind of fraud or corruption can be totally eliminated.
4	Cloud Computing Technology	Use of external hardware, software, or software applications ubiquitously by a company or individuals as rented or free facility for used time so that physical owning of such facilities can be eliminated. This will optimize the utilization of any digital storage and processing device by sharing with other users globally for rent.
5	Cyber Security Technology	Used for providing the security and secrecy of data, information in digital devices during processing, storing, and transmission stages as well for identifying the actual user of a system. Cyber security technology has responsibility to protect computers, networks, programs, and data for any kind of exploitation from unauthorized access or attacks.
6	3D Printing Technology	Using 3D Printing technology, any device or structure made

		of any material including, plastic, rubber, metals, mud, cement, or their mixtures in any proportion and in any size can be fabricated layer by layer into a three dimensional structure to produce real devices and systems.
7	Digital Marketing Technology	Digital marketing technology allows the companies and individuals to sell their products and services to entire world by means low cost, affordable ubiquitous marketing techniques using internet.
8	Internet & Internet of Things (IOT)	Internet of things technology (IoT) is used to communicate, control, and monitor various digital devices used in home, office, and company environment interconnected using internet. IOT has major application in interconnecting various cyber-physical systems in industry 4.0.
9	Information Storage Technology	This technology supports the development of high density digital and optical storage devices of capability Terabytes, Petabytes, Exabytes, Zettabytes, and Yottabytes.
10	Optical Computing Technology	Fabrication of high speed optical computers based on optical signal switching and optical signal processing using optical logic gates and flip-flops by means suitable materials/devices.
11	Online Education Technology	Allows to transform traditional campus based education into Massive Online Open Courses (MOOC) based education. Ex : EDX, COUSERA, NPTEL, SWAYAM, etc.
12	Virtual and Augmented Reality	Create an artificial environment to mimic the real situations with the help of a computer machine and presented to a user in such a way that the user suspends the belief and accepts it as a real environment. It has applications in entertainment and education. Augmented reality is a pseudo or mixed reality of real and virtual worlds by the assistance of a computer-generated perceptual information and used to enhance customer experience in business services.

The above ICCT underlying technologies are capable to solve many problems related to human comfortability and dreamy desires. These underlying technologies along with a suitable manufacturing technology can do marvel to solving many problems of the individuals of society. ICCT at its nascent stage, is expected to support the production of super intelligent machines which can replace human employees by robots in many industries.

3.2 Nanotechnology Underlying Technologies :

Nanotechnology is another general purpose technology supports manufacturing of various products using special properties of Nanoparticles (10⁻⁹ m). It is a manufacturing technology with potential ability to improve the features of existing products and to produce new products in various fields. Nanotechnology has many subfields called nanotechnology underlying technologies. Nanotechnology is a boon to the mankind if handled carefully. Nanotechnology is capable to solve problems of basic types, advanced problems related to human comfortability, and even problems related to dreamy desires if used with other application type technologies like

ICCT. Nanotechnology can solve problems related to providing nutritious food by producing artificial food, converting environmental water and sea water into drinking water in large scale using renewable energy, providing low cost and strong shelters at low cost, low cost renewable energy to required amount, solutions to low cost and durable transportation facility, durable consumer products and textiles, easy health and medical solutions. Nanotechnology at its nascent stage, is expected to support for the production of self-replicating nanomachines which can further build any structure as per the requirement. The important underlying technologies of nanotechnology are listed below :

- (1) Nanomaterials development Technology
- (2) Nanomechanics Technology
- (3) Nanoelectronics Technology
- (4) Nanophotonics Technology
- (5) Nanobiotechnology
- (6) Nanomedicine

Applications of Nanotechnology underlying Technologies :

Nanomaterials of suitable type and properties are used in Nanotechnology treated Seeds in Agriculture, in food packets, production of artificial food, Customized location focused rain and large scale production of drinking water from sea & environment, nanomaterial fabricated textiles with many special properties, nanomaterial based cosmetics, paints, consumer durables, building materials, improving products quality, durability in many industries, etc. Nanomechanics Technology is used in manufacturing equipment, nanoelectromechanical systems (NEMS) etc. Nanoelectronics Technology is used in production and use of nanodiodes, nanotransistors, Nano integrated circuits, and nanostructure based electronic memories. Nanophotonics Technology deals with nanomaterial based solar cells, optical memories, optical computers, etc. Nanobiotechnology deals with bio-medical applications of nanomaterials including drug delivery, targeted therapy, Gene delivery, Molecular imaging, Bio-marker mapping, detection & diagnosis of diseases etc. Nanomedicine has subareas like biological imaging for diagnostics, Biosensors for toxin detection, Regenerative medicine, Medical robotics, nanobots, Tissue engineering, Drug delivery, cancer therapy, surgery, etc.

Apart from above, nanotechnology has its roots in many different areas to solve basic problems, advanced requirements, and dreamy desires along with other technologies including ICCT. Such breakthrough technologies of the 21st century include :

- (i) Nanotechnology treated Seeds for Innovations in Agriculture
- (ii) Universal drinking water system
- (iii) Automobiles
- (iv) Renewable energy system
- (v) Optical computation
- (vi) Embedded intelligence
- (vii) Chameleon chips
- (viii) Space Travel
- (ix) Anticipated Immortality

Table 2 : Prominent applications of NT underlying technologies

S. No.	Underlying Technologies	Prominent Applications
1	Nanomaterials development Technology	Applications related to Nanometal chemistry, Nanostructured polymers, Nanocomposites, etc for cosmetics, textiles, consumer products, agriculture, food

		processing and packaging, water filters, etc.
2	Nanomechanics Technology	Deals with mechanical properties (kinetic, thermal, and elastic) of physical systems having nanometer material involved in them. Used in nanotriobiology for friction, wears and contact mechanics at nano scale electromagnetic systems, and nanofluidics. Many kinds of chemical compounds, advanced mechanical motors, UPS and high-power batteries, horsepower, acidic fuels, rust disinfectants, Nanotubes and Carbon Nanowires, Nanolithography, Nanomanufacturing, Nanolithography, and other areas of manufacturing.
3	Nanoelectronics Technology	Nanofabrication, Nanoprocessors, nanotransistors, Nanoelectronic components for high temperature, ultra - low power, biologically friendly packaging, Nanoelectronic memories, etc.
4	Nanophotonics Technology	Nanocomputers, Nanosensors, Nanoprobes, fluorescent imaging, sensitization, nanolithography. All optical processors, Bio-imaging, Energy conversion, Molecular manipulation, Data storage, Display devices, etc.
5	Nanobiotechnology	Pre-clinical Testing of Novel Nano Medical tools, Diagnostic Tools and Applications, Tissue, Cell and Genetic Engineering involving Nano Medical Tools, Protein detection, genome sequencing, proteomics, imaging, nanobots, and self-replicating; pesticide delivery systems through bioactive nanoencapsulation; biosensors to detect and quantify pathogens; organic compounds, etc.
6	Nanomedicine	Therapeutic advancements using Nano-medicine and Research Techniques, Development of Nano Drug Delivery Systems, Cancer treatment, Gene therapy, treatment of neurodegenerative disorders, operative dentistry, Antibacterial treatment, Ophthalmology, Surgery, Tissue engineering, Regenerative medicine, Cell repair, Medicated textiles, etc.

4. Unification of ICCT & Nanotechnologies :

It can be argued that the nanotechnology underlying technologies and ICCT underlying technologies are related and depending on each other. Nanotechnology is manufacturing technology and ICCT is an application technology. The innovations in nanotechnology support innovations in ICCT and Opportunities in ICCT stimulates innovations in Nanotechnology. Thus, nanotechnology and ICCT are complementary and interdependent technologies. When these two technologies are studied together, the researchers will get a better idea to innovate in their thinking to solve many kinds of problems in society. The term unification is used to combine two or more things which can be used together to solve a problem. Unification of two technologies means these two technologies can be used together to get a complete solution to a real-world problem. Unification of ICCT and Nanotechnologies leads to an accelerated growth of these technologies and innovations in nanotechnology support further innovations in ICCT or vice versa. Such unified technology also allows them to solve basic problems, advanced problems and dreamy desires of the peoples of society. Such unification leads to universal technology as discussed in section 3.

Table 3 : ICCT and NT underlying technologies which show complementary properties for unification

S. No.	NT Underlying Technologies	ICCT Underlying Technologies
1	Nanomaterials development Technology	Artificial Intelligence, 3D Printing, Blockchain,
2	Nanomechanics Technology	Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence
3	Nanoelectronics Technology	Artificial Intelligence Data & Business Analytics, Internet of Things, Blockchain,
4	Nanophotonics Technology	Optical Computing, Blockchain,
5	Nanobiotechnology	Artificial Intelligence, 3D Printing,
6	Nanomedicine	Artificial Intelligence, Virtual Reality

5. Redefining the Manufacturing Industry based on Unified Universal Technology :

Manufacturing industry converts raw materials into finished products for basic needs, comfortable wants, and even for dreamy desires of human beings. The usage of special raw materials with ideal characteristics or improved characteristics may lead to ideal or improved products having improved properties. Similarly automating manufacturing processes with high precision and for negligible maintenance cost. Further, the final product manufactured should be an innovative product and have multi features compared to similar products available in the market. Using nanomaterials and devices as raw materials, ICCT underlying technologies like Artificial intelligence, IoT, 3D printing, etc. in the manufacturing industry sector can fulfil these possibilities. It is argued that most of the future products produced in the manufacturing industry will use nanotechnology and ICCT underlying technologies as universal technology to redefine the manufacturing industry.

6. Redefining the Service Industry based on Unified Universal Technology :

Service sector is another important sector in business management and is mainly dependent on technology. Both nanotechnology and ICCT are expected to impact heavily and creates many breakthroughs in service sectors. The nanotechnology underlying technologies like nanomedicine, nanobiotechnology, nanodevices of nanomechanics, nanoelectronics, and nanophotonics are expected to support service industry along with their complementary ICCT underlying technologies like artificial intelligence, IOT, cloud computing, optical computers, virtual realities etc. It is strongly believed that both nanotechnology and ICCT together as universal technology will redefine the service sector present models and contribute heavily on solving problems related to the basic needs, comfortable wants, and even for dreamy desires of human beings. Thus, service industry has opportunity to adopt NT and ICCT components to improve the service quality and service features.

7. MANAGEMENT OF UNIVERSAL TECHNOLOGY :

The identification and implementation of suitable technologies in various business processes for a given organization is possible by means of (1) predicting future technologies, (2) anticipating the breakthrough technologies, (3) Choosing a suitable emerging technology, (4) Analysing for organizational business & corporate innovation, (5) Planning for adoption of emerging technology, (6) Analysing the cost-benefit of new technology, (7) Technology adoption, (8) Technology customization, (9) Technology monitoring & control, (10) Verifying productivity or performance, and (11) Scanning the environment for further technology breakthroughs. The

systematic study of using these steps for the strategic management of technology for enhancing and controlling the productivity and performance of a given organization.

(1) Predicting future technologies :

The managers at the executive level have the responsibility of setting the future plans called the strategic plans of the organization. They should continuously monitor the changes in technology, changes in business models, and changes in customers perception with time. Predicting future technologies is a very important requirement of managing the business for sustainability.

(2) Anticipating the breakthrough technologies:

Managers while predicting future technologies need to anticipate the major breakthroughs in technology in a given time frame and plan their business investments and expansion accordingly. Breakthrough technologies may convert into killer technologies and may make the present business model or products or services obsolete.

(3) Choosing a suitable emerging technology :

Managers as decision makers to lead the organization or departments take responsibility of monitoring the external environment for possible changes in the business environment and adopt changes accordingly. When they realize the advents of technologies are going to affect the organizational performance, they should adopt such changes and if the changes are technology driven, they have a responsibility to identify an alternative which is optimum for their organizations within their constraints by choosing a suitable emerging technology as strategic alternative.

(4) Analysing for organizational business & corporate innovation :

While choosing an emerging technology as a strategic alternative, managers have to analyse their present business, historical changes in their business model and its effect on their organizational performance, using various internal analysis and external analysis techniques [10]. This analysis should also involve the various innovations implemented and expected in the same industrial sector.

(5) Planning for adoption of emerging technology :

Based on the analysis of various alternative technologies and choosing one optimum technology, the manager should plan for adopting the new technology in organizational processes. This include short term plan and long term plan and the systematic procedure of adoption to various sections, branches, and subsidiaries.

(6) Analysing the cost-benefit of new technology :

The managers have responsibility on analysing the cost of such new technology based investment. In order to make use of emerging new technologies for organizational benefits, one of the techniques is to analyse the cost of adopting and implementation and its future benefits for the organization for a fixed period of time. Strategical analysis of cost-benefit will allow managers to make a decision related to the investment in new emerging technology and the speed of adoption in the organization.

(7) Technology adoption,

One, the organization decides to adopt a particular technology based on cost-benefit analysis, it has to identify suitable vendors to supply or to develop such technological applications.

(8) Technology customization :

The organization should effectively utilize the newly adopted technology as per their requirement by customizing them to be suitable for organizational use.

(9) Technology monitoring & control :

The purpose of technology monitoring and control is to gather information about the operational status and the capability of new technology adopted to improve the quality and efficiency of various processes and the product or service developed. A proper feedback mechanism and control based on feedback on effect of new technology should be in place to monitor organizational performance.

(10) Verifying productivity or performance :

This step includes the study of the effect of newly adopted technology on the efficiency and effectiveness of various organizational processes or new processes developed. The organization should develop a suitable mechanism to determine and compare the efficiency and effectiveness after the adoption of new technology with previous technology. In this process, the organization should try to measure the improvement in productivity and performance as well as the implication of such innovation on the organizational value chain as well as the brand for future growth and prosperity.

(11) Scanning the environment for further technology breakthroughs :

The strategic management of the universal technology model involves continuous monitoring the emerging technologies and possible technology breakthroughs in society. A strategic organization involves itself or through collaboration, involves in development of new technology which is relevant to its business area. Scanning the environment to watch the progress and foresee the changes is a continuous process for every organization competing in the global business environment.

The above eleven steps are essential as “Lifecycle stages of the model on strategic management of technology” in any organization for enhancing and controlling the productivity and performance. These lifecycle stages are essential in strategic management of technology in any organization for growth and prosperity.

8. REACHING TECHNOLOGICAL SINGULARITY :

Super intelligent machines are expected to be developed using ICCT underlying technologies and nanotechnology [9]. Similarly, nanotechnology along with ICCT underlying technologies are expected to create super human beings by modifying gene and body cells which may give rise to human immortality [11]. It is also predicted that the super intelligent machines are capable to replicate in any level of accelerated pace using a process called self-replication. The ability of self-replication of nanomachines and their super human intelligence leads to a stage so called technological singularity. It is defined as a hypothetical event in which artificial intelligence technology would be capable to build intelligent machines in the process of an intelligence explosion, that yields a super-intelligent machine which surpasses all current human control or understanding [12], [13], [14].

Thus, technological singularity is a point in the future time scale where (1) machines can think, work, and decide faster than human beings, (2) Some human beings converts themselves as super human beings using technology and achieve immortality, and (3) Direct interactions between computers and human brains leads to human- machine ubiquitous interaction. It is predicted that by the year 2050, scientists will achieve technological singularity and its consequences both positive and negative. The strategic management of technological singularity which is the consequences of Nanotechnology underlying technologies and ICCT underlying technologies is expected to play a major role in managing disasters and offering advantages related to the growth and prospers to the society.

9. CONCLUSION :

Managing technology is an important area of business management. Managing business in different industrial sectors needs the knowledge of technologies and knowledge of changes in technologies. Many general purpose technologies developed during the last few decades and supported to various industrial sectors for fast contribution to the civilized society. Technology which is an application of science to solve different problems in society is expected to reach its highest expected stage in the 21st century and gave rise to two general purpose technologies called ICCT and Nanotechnology. These two technologies are capable to solve many problems leading to optimized solutions at basic, advanced, and desired level of the society. This paper made an elaborative analysis on how the emerging general purpose technologies can grow and integrate themselves into universal technology to solve many problems in society to give a comfortable life to everyone in society. Adding further, it is essential to plan and manage these technologies in organizations systematically using our lifecycle model of technology implementation and management due to the fact that these integrated universal technologies have both positive and negative effects while using in different industries due to their anticipated capability of elevating to the technological singularity.

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A STUDY ON HEALTH INSURANCE-AWARENESS AND WELL-BEING OF HUMANS

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ABSTRACT

Health insurance playing a major role as a protection for health is one of the rapidly growing sectors in the Indian economy. People are being conscious about their well-being both in rural and urban areas. Health insurance is not only provided by the government of India, it is provided by the private insurance companies also. There needs to be proper awareness about the benefits offered by these insurance companies by including subjects on insurance and banking in the academics, mobile vans, integrating of all the affiliated hospitals in the Google maps etc. and also understand the underlying facts of being insured. Before an individual gets himself insured, it becomes a necessity to analyse the opportunities available and the costs associated with it. The major opportunities offered by the health insurance are for the educated youths, middle class, BPL card holders etc. At the same time there are reasons as to why individuals do not prefer health insurance and the reasons may vary with regard to the schemes offered to the public. Health insurance protects the individuals by paying huge amount of medical services with the payment of considerable premium amount in return and this can be partial or full amount. The insurance companies should carefully frame their messages or the content that influence the public in acquiring such insurance schemes. When there are many plans being offered, the individuals need to analyse the loop holes of it and then proceed further and this requires proper understanding of those plans.

Ayushman Bharat Yojana is a newly launched scheme by the Central Government of India in the year 2018, and its main aim being covering both preventing and promoting health, to largely address healthcare. It is expected to cover approximately 10 crore poor families for time being by setting up 1.5 lakhs wellness centres across the country. In order to provide cashless benefits E- cards had been generated and are trying to pool in more private hospitals along with government hospitals to provide this scheme and its benefits.

This paper showcases the awareness level of health insurance amongst people residing in Bangalore and their opinion regarding the newly launched scheme 'Ayushman Bharat'.

Keywords – Health insurance, government and private schemes, opportunities and access, urban and rural people, Ayushman Bharat.

INTRODUCTION

Health insurance is an insurance that acts as a protection that covers the cost that an individual incurs with regard medical, surgical and hospitalization expenses. Health insurance is a form of insurance cover where an individual and the insurance provider enters into a contract, where in the latter will agree to compensate at the time of occurrence of any uncertain event from the premium paid by the individual. There is no maturity of this policy that is the amount will not be paid back to the insured until and unless any uncertain event occurs.

At some point in life people probably need expensive medical care. Health insurance like other kinds of insurance protects those individuals against significant financial loss. Thus this can be in the form of two basic plans which are group plans and individual plans. A group buys insurance for everyone in the group which is less expensive and members belonging to the group can enroll even if pre-existing conditions exist whereas individual plans are customizable to match individual's personal needs and is comparatively more expensive to group plans.

The health care expenditure of few countries are like UK is 8.4%, Brazil is 7.5%, Cambodia is 12%, China is 8%, Ghana is 5.6%, Indonesia is 4%, Mexico is 6.1%, Sri Lanka is 3.7% and this is with reference from recent past data.

HEALTH INSURANCE IN INDIA

The health insurance industry in India was launched in 1986 and witnessed a rapid growth in the 1990's economic reforms and general awareness. The India's health system became one of the largest in the world having beneficiaries of 1.3 billion people is an emerging segment of India's economy. The Indians prefer individual health insurance plans over the group health insurance plans. According to WHO, the Indians out of their expenses 9% of the people prefer group insurance and 82% of the people prefer individual insurance.

Ayushman Bharat, the world's biggest health care scheme was launched on 23rd September 2018 by Prime Minister Modi in Ranchi. The scheme has been renamed as Prime Minister Jan Arogya Yojana. About 50 crores citizen are stand to the benefit offering insurance of Rs 5 lakh per family covering the poor and economically backward sections. The entire process of Ayushman Bharat is digitalized in all the hospitals empanelled with the scheme. No premium is collected from the beneficiaries to take the insurance cover. The medical expense for secondary and tertiary care procedure comes under the ambit of the scheme. Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana , Senior Citizen Health Insurance Scheme, Central Government Health Scheme, Employee's State Insurance Scheme etc; are the multiple schemes which are subsumed in the National Health Protection Scheme that is AYUSHMAN BHARAT.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyze and understand the awareness of health insurance in India.
- To study the opinion about the newly launched scheme 'Ayushman Bharat'.
- To study the behavioral pattern of people towards the health insurance.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- Research paper limits to the aspect of understanding the level of awareness about health insurance
- To understand the gap between the health insurance schemes and the beneficiaries.
- To study the effectiveness of Ayushman Bharath among the respondents.
- Research paper is focused on government health insurance schemes

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The Indian health insurance sector is growing since the 1990's but at a slower pace and the main reason being lack of awareness about the opportunities that is offered to the citizens. Even though there are many schemes which is not being effectively communicated to the people and this creates a gap between the schemes providers and the beneficiaries of the scheme. Therefore there is a need to understand the actual reason as to why people do not take health insurance.

BENEFITS OF HEALTH INSURANCE

- If the person is insured with health insurance cashless treatment is provided to them by the insurance companies that works in collaboration with the respective hospitals
- Medical inflation can be met by having a health insurance
- Premium paid on health insurance is tax deductible under section 80D of Income tax Act
- Periodic health check up to the policyholders of health insurance and it is cashless if the tests are done at the empanelled hospitals or centres.

METHODOLOGY

The research on health insurance – awareness and well-being of humans was based on both primary data and secondary data. The primary data was collected from the questionnaire from a sample of 116 students from urban and rural area of Bangalore and represented in the form of graphs. The secondary data was collected from the online websites relating health insurance and a couple of books. This data was classified and tabulated. Findings have been summarized and suggestions have been made.

LIMITATIONS

- The primary data of this research was randomly collected from the people residing in Bangalore both urban and rural.
- The research mainly focuses on present scenario of health insurance where in few of the respondents are not aware of the benefits through health insurance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A number of research papers and articles provide a detailed insight about the health insurance and a view about its opportunities and challenges in India.

Binny, Dr Meenu Gupta (2017), the authors have analysed that the insurance sector in India is growing rapidly in both urban and rural areas and yet there exists a between citizens of India and insurance service providers because of lack of awareness and also because of complexity in the structure in the form of high claim ratios, less understanding of products, changing needs

of the customers etc.,

Shefali Malhotra, Ira Patnak, Shubho Roy and Ajay Shah,10/5/2018. This research paper talks about Indian Health Care, their analyses of the claim ratio and the complaints rates are increasing, suggests that there are problems in health insurance. This is because of deficiencies in regulations, weak enforcement of regulations and faulty institutional design of consumer redress. The solutions are in the law framing.

K Swathi, R Anuradha (2018), the authors talk about the awareness created by the General Insurance Corporation of India and the insurance regulatory and development authority and to reduce the procrastination for buying the health insurance. They also mentioned about the transition due to introduction of private health care financing, increased income, health consciousness among different classes of the society.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE STUDY

Table no 1 showing the occupation of the respondents

Occupation	percentage
Students	40%
Tax analysts	9%
Business	3%
Others	42%

From the above table it is analysed that the majority of the respondents are the students who are in their 20s and the next highest being the tax analysts comprising of 9% , the business category comprises of 3% and the remaining 42% is by the other occupational categories like agriculture, managers, service providers etc; therefore it can be inferred that the study majorly comprises of the students.

Chart no 1 showing the occupation of the respondents

Table no 2: Showing the percentage of respondents in rural and urban region

Region	percentage
Rural	28%
Urban	72%

The above table shows the region of the respondents that is urban or rural of Bangalore. The table shows that 72% of the respondents are from the urban area and the remaining 28% of the respondents are from the rural area. Therefore it can be inferred that this study majorly comprises of the opinions of people from urban area.

Chart no 2. Showing the number of respondents from rural or urban

Table no 3: Showing the awareness of respondents regarding health insurance

Awareness	percentages
Yes	95%
No	5%

The above table shows about the awareness level of health insurance in India. Out of the all the respondents 5% of the people are not aware of the existence of the health insurance schemes and policies. This may be because of the varied reasons and the remaining 95% of the respondents are aware of it but not necessarily owning a health insurance. Therefore it can be inferred that with the growth in insurance sector the awareness level is also increasing but there people who are totally unaware about it and certain actions needs to be taken to overcome this.

Chart no 3. Showing the awareness of the respondents

Table no 4. Showing the sources through which the respondents get the information on health insurance

Sources	Percentages
TV Ads	59%
Internet	56%
Friends/ Relatives	48%
Others (Average)	12.42%

The above table shows the major sources from where the respondents receive information about health insurance. 59% of the information is received from television ads, then 56% of them received information from internet , 48% of the information from friends and relatives and the remaining from other sources like company brochure, hospitals etc.

Therefore it can be inferred that the major information is being received from both traditional and modern forms of information spreading and these sources can be used to create more awareness.

Chart no 4. Showing the various sources through which the respondents get the information on health insurance

Table no 5. Showing the type of message of health insurance which influences the respondents

Type of messages	Percentages
Family Health protection	52%
Fear of big houses	20%
Health risk cover	16%
Well -being and health	10%
Not applicable	2%

The above table shows that what kind of messages from the health insurance companies influence the individuals to buy a health insurance. Majority of the respondents that is 52% give importance to the family health protection, 20% of them because of the fear of huge expenses and out of the remaining 28% , 2% of the respondents belong to not applicable category as they are not aware of health insurance. Therefore we can infer that the individuals in India give more importance to the family and their health than other factors.

Chart no 5. Showing the type of message of health insurance which influences the respondents

Table no 6. Showing the most used source for meeting the medical expenses of the respondents

Sources	percentages
Health care for product	46%
Own savings	35%
Health insurance	8%
Group health insurance from employer/association	11%

The above table shows the most used source of fund for meeting the respondents medical expenses. 46% of them usually spend money on health from their own savings, 35% of them rely on health insurance, 11% solely on the government health care and 8% on the health insurance availed by them through employment. Therefore it can be inferred that the respondents rely more on their savings rather than health insurance because of unawareness and lack of guarantee for the medical expenses to be met at the right time.

Chart no 6. Showing the most used source of fund for meeting the medical expenses among the respondents

Table no 7. Showing the awareness of the respondents regarding the various health insurance schemes

SCHEMES	PERCENTAGES
RASHTRIYA SWASTHYA BIMA YOJANA	36%
ESI SCHEME	27%
CENTRAL GOVERNMENT HEALTH SCHEMES	20%
UNIVERSAL HEALTH SCHEMES	22%
AYUSHMAN BHARATH	51%
STATE GOVERNMENT SCHEMES	24%

The above table shows the awareness of health insurance schemes that is available for the people. 51% of the respondents are aware about Ayushman Bharath, 36 % of them are aware about the Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana, and the remaining 13% of them are aware about ESI, state government schemes etc. Therefore it can be inferred

Chart no 7 Showing the awareness of the respondents to various health insurance schemes

Table no 8. Showing the reasons for opting a health insurance policy

Reasons	percentages
To protect from rising cost of health care	65%
Uncertain Health problems	59%
Tax benefits	14%
Reducing out of pocket expenses	24%
Attractive schemes are available	2%

From the above table we can understand that there are few reasons which influence the people to take up the health insurance policy. From the survey the respondents opted for health insurance policy for the reasons such as to protect the rising cost of health care, uncertain health problems, tax benefits, to reduce out of pocket expenses etc., Therefore it can be inferred that 65% of the respondents opted for health insurance scheme to protect from the rising cost of health care followed by 59% for uncertain health problems.

Chart no 8. Showing the reasons for opting health insurance policy

Table no 9. Showing the reasons why people don't take up health insurance

Reasons	percentages
Did not feel the need	14%
No returns on investment	13%
High premium charged	20%
Poor services provided and coverage	16%
Complicated terms and conditions	37%

From the above table we can understand that there are few reasons which hinders the people not to take up the health insurance policy such as no returns on investment like life insurance, high premium charged, complicated terms and conditions etc., Therefore it can be inferred that 37% of the respondents did not take up the policy due to the complicated terms and

conditions in the policy where as 20% of the respondents felt that high premiums charged were the reason followed by 16% felt that due to poor services and coverage were the reasons for them not to take the policy.

Chart no 9. Showing the reasons of the respondents for not taking up the health insurance

Table no 10. Showing preferences of respondents regarding the schemes

Preferences	Percentages
Government schemes	16%
Private schemes	16%
Both	68%

From the above table we can understand that there is preference among the people while selecting the schemes. Therefore it can be inferred that equal number of respondents prefer government and private schemes i.e. 16% where as 68% of the respondents prefer a combination of government and private scheme.

Chart no 10. Showing the preferences of respondents regarding the schemes

Table no 11. Showing the schemes offered by the government will be available at the right time

Availability of schemes	Percentages
Yes	13%
No	18%
Maybe	69%

The above table shows the availability of government schemes at the right time. Therefore it is inferred that 13% of the respondents feel that the schemes provided by the government will be available at right time where as 18% of the respondents feel that the schemes are not available at the right time. And the majority of the respondents are unsure whether the schemes will be available at the right time or not.

Chart no 11. Showing the schemes offered by the government will be available at the right time

Table no 12. Showing the awareness of Ayushman Bharath

Awareness	Percentages
Yes	58%
No	42%

The above table shows the awareness of the people regarding the newly launched health protection scheme i.e. Ayushman Bharath. Therefore it can be inferred that majority of the respondents are aware of Ayushman Bharath i.e. 58% and 42% of the respondents are not aware of this scheme. There is no much difference between the respondents who are aware and the respondents who are unaware.

Chart no. 12 showing the awareness of Ayushman Bharath

Table no 13. Showing the effectiveness of Ayushman Bharath

Effective	Percentages
yes	75%
No (total)	25%

The above table shows the effectiveness of the newly launched National Health Protection Scheme i.e. Ayushman Bharath. Therefore it can be inferred that 75% of the respondents feel that this scheme will be effective where as 25% of the respondents feel that it will not be effective giving the reasons such as unawareness, less private hospital being empanelled under the scheme, when all the citizens will be benefited from the scheme.

Chart no 13. Showing the effectiveness of Ayushman Bharath

FINDINGS

- With the growth in insurance sector the awareness level is also increasing but there are people who are totally unaware about it and certain actions needs to be taken to overcome this.
- The major information is being received from both traditional and modern forms of information spreading like Tv Ads, Internet, friends or relatives etc.,
- The individuals in India give more importance to the family and their health than other factors.
- The respondents rely more on their savings rather than health insurance because of unawareness and lack of guarantee for the medical expenses to be met at the right time.
- The recently launched scheme, Ayushman Bharat is gaining popularity amongst the people and this is because of its opportunities and benefits offered to the citizens of India.
- The respondents opted for health insurance policy for the reasons such as medical inflation, uncertain health problems, tax benefits, to reduce out of pocket expenses etc.,
- Few reasons which hinders the people not to take up the health insurance policy such as no returns on investment like life insurance, high premium charged, complicated terms and conditions etc.,
- Majority of the respondents are unsure whether the schemes will be available at the right time or not.
- Respondents are of the opinion that the Ayushman Bharath will be effective if it covers all the citizens in the country

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Subjects like insurance and banking must be included in the academics which helps to create awareness.
- Regular awareness campaign must be conducted by the respective local municipalities and analyse the improvements and developments in their jurisdiction by using mobile vans.
- There is a communication gap between the insurance providers and the beneficiaries this is majorly seen in rural region and hence this can be reduced by communicating in the regional languages.
- The country is moving towards digitalization so the technology must be used for verifying the beneficiaries mainly rural people with the help of biometric systems if they fail to carry the scheme card.
- Not all the individuals in India are employed and out of all those employed do not receive high salary and savings made from this form is not sufficient to meet the uncertain events and hence owning a health insurance proves to beneficial.
- For senior citizen and child care there must be special package where the limit can be increased
- Individuals who feel that there is no return on investment should take up health insurance schemes which has low premium to be paid.

CONCLUSION

Economic growth is a major indicator of countries well-being and development. Empirical studies suggest that a significant portion of economic growth is contributed by human capital. The two major contributors of human capital are the elements of level of education and health of the people.

Health insurance in India being the major sector of growth is gaining popularity at large because of its opportunities and benefits that is offered to the citizens of India by the health insurance service providers. These services are offered by both government and the private health insurance agencies to compensate at the time of occurrence of any uncertain event. Along with the opportunities and benefits it also has challenges which act as a major drawback for the Indian citizens (about 78% of the population of India) has no form of health insurance. The reasons being lack of awareness of the existing health insurance schemes, deficiency in the regulation of health insurance, complexity in the structure of the system, faulty institutional design of consumer redress and many more. India with the population of 1.3 billion possess around 18% of the global population and around 22% of the global disease burden. India ranks 154th on the health care index Global Burden of Disease study (GBD). More than 78 to 83% of health care expenditure in India is met out of individuals' pockets'.

And therefore in order to provide more benefits there is a need to step up health care funding mechanism. The cost of health insurance depends on the age, sum assured, the current health status, lifestyle etc. Only 2% of India's population consciously decides to buy health insurance and there is 9.6% of contribution by health insurance in India to the general insurance market. The rural population spends on an average Rs.5636 for the hospitalized treatment in a public sector hospital and Rs. 21726 at a private sector hospital.

Even though this sector is growing there are certain hindrances which need to be overcome like increasing the awareness level through certain officials like corporator, MLA, MP of the respective locality, there must be proper utilization of the technology like artificial intelligence, proper grievance redressal mechanism etc., and one such recently launched scheme is Ayushman Bharath which is currently showing a positive growth scale. Ayushman Bharath is gaining popularity but the awareness level has to be further pushed across the country and there must be more clarity in the message that is being conveyed.

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A STUDY ON TASTE AND PREFERENCE OF RURAL POPULATION TOWARDS USED PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MOODABIDRI, D.K

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ABSTRACT

A second-hand or used good is one that is being purchased by or otherwise transferred to second or later end user. Second hand items may be transfer between friends or family for free, or they can be sold at lower price at garage sales. Many people prefer to buy new goods, since new goods can make them feel safer. A warranty is provided for new goods they can fix for free or simply change a new one, buy new goods also can avoid buying stolen goods. But second-hand goods has significant benefits such as prevent them becoming waste and saves costly production of equivalent new goods. It can conserving natural resources and protecting the environment, and may from part of a simple living plan. The second-hand market is exciting developing now. Since global financial crisis hit, people turn to shopping in an economy way, so the second hand trading market benefit from this struggling economy. Therefore marketing of used products is a good marketing opportunity. This study gives some suggestions to improve the used products marketing strategy in rural selling and market promotion strategies framed by analysing rural buying behaviour.

Keywords:

New goods, second-hand goods, Market, Opportunity.

INTRODUCTION

A second-hand or used good is a piece of personal property that is being purchased by or otherwise transferred to a second or later end user. Second-hand goods can benefit the purchaser as the price paid is lower than that of the same items bought new. If the reduction in price more than compensates for the possibly shorter remaining lifetime, lack of warranty, and so on, there is a net benefit. Selling unwanted second hand goods instead of discarding them obviously benefits the seller.

Recycling goods through the second hand market reduces use of resources in manufacturing new goods, and diminishes waste which must be disposed of, both of which are significant environmental benefits. However, manufacturers who profit from sales of new goods lose corresponding sales. Scientific research shows that buying used goods reduces carbon footprint and CO₂ emissions significantly compared to the complete product life cycle, because of less production, raw material sourcing and logistics. Often the relative carbon footprint of production,

raw material sourcing and the supply chain is unknown. A scientific methodology has been made to analyse how much CO2 emissions are reduced when buying used goods like second hand hardware versus new hardware.

Quality of second-hand goods can be more durable than equivalent new goods. Second-hand goods may have faults which are not apparent even if examined; purchasing sight unseen, for example, from an Internet auction site, has further unknowns. Goods may cause problems beyond their value; for example, furniture may have not easily seen bedbugs, which may cause an infestation which is difficult and expensive to eradicate. Faulty electrical and mechanical goods can be hazardous and dangerous.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- i. To identify difficulties for marketing of used products,
- ii. To analyze opportunities in rural area for marketing of used products,
- iii. To study the opinion of people about consumption of used products,
- iv. To determine factors influencing the purchase of used products in rural area,
- v. To suggest effective strategies for marketing of used products.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The study is conducted based on the respondent in Moodabidri area and study is undertaken in order to find consumer behaviour towards second-hand products. This study helps to know the challenges and opportunities to marketing of used products and to determine factors influencing on purchase of used products.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- The researcher has used both primary and secondary source of data collection i.e. through questioner and direct interview method and also through social media.
- The sample size taken for the present study by the researcher is 55 respondents out of 150 respondents, For this study, the special reference is given to the Moodabidri region which includes Moodabidri, kallamundkur, Sampige and Aikala
- The study was conducted for nearly 2 months i.e. from June to August.

DATA SOURCE:

- **Primary data:** The researcher has used primary source of data collection i.e. through questioner and direct interview method.
- **Secondary data:** The paper also took help of secondary data like various research papers, journals, newspapers, and online data base.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

- The primary data is collected from the people who are living in Moodabidri area only.

- Most of the data collected both from primary as well as secondary, but no statistical techniques used.
- Due to non-availability of all the facts and figures a detailed study was difficult.
- The collected information subject to bias as the study also includes secondary information.

SOCIAL RELEVANCE OF THE STUDY

This study mainly concentrate on analyzing taste and preference of rural people towards used products, and also states the difficulties for marketing of used products and problems of rural people in their area, consumption of used products helps to save natural resources. This study also helps to analyze opportunities in rural area for marketing of used products and to determine factors influencing the purchase of used products in rural area. This study suggests the effective strategies for marketing of used products in rural area. The demand for second hand goods now a days increasing, this study educates about business opportunity for marketing of used product in rural area.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table No: 1. Demand for Second hand products.

Sl. No	Option	Responses	Percentage
1	White goods	10	18%
2	Auto mobile	21	38%
3	Furniture	7	13%
4	Books	17	31%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

The above table represents that 18% of people have interest towards white goods, 38% of people ready to buy auto mobile products, 13% people demands Furniture products and 31% people

have interest to purchase second hand books. Most of the responses are partially favourable towards auto mobile goods and second hand books, the main reason for more demand for auto mobile goods is they can resale purchased second hand auto mobile product and the reason for high demand for books is students are not ready to spent huge money on new books. Auto mobile goods and second hand books are having more demand compare to other products.

Table no: 2. Purpose of purchasing used products.

Sl. No	Options	No. of response	Percentage
1	For use	38	69%
2	For resale	13	24%
3	Other	4	7%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above diagram will come to know that 69% people buy used products for final consumption, 24% people purchase used products for resale and 7% people purchasing used products for other purpose like using important parts of used products. Many people purchasing used products for final consumption because the price of new products is high and most of rural people are having less income to buy new products.

It is interpreted that majority of the people are purchasing used products for final consumption.

Table no: 3 Purchase of used products.

Sl. No	Options	No of response	Percentage
1	Directly from owner	31	56%
2	Online	8	15%
3	Retailer	16	29%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above diagram will come to know that 56% people purchases used products directly from owners, 15% people buying used products through online website and remaining 29% people purchasing second hand products from retailers or shops. The main reason for purchasing used product directly from owner is people feel safe about their product and online purchasing is very less because people think that for purchasing used products online websites are not safe and chances of fraud is more.

Majority of people purchasing used products directly from owners in rural area and few people prefer online website to purchase used products.

Table no: 4. Money willing to pay to purchase used products

Sl. No	Options	No of response	Percentage
1	Below 5,000	17	31%
2	5,000-20,000	31	56%
3	20,000-30,000	5	9%
4	Above 30,000	2	4%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

The most of the people of this place are middle class and below poverty line. 31% people ready to purchase any used products for 5000 rupees, 56% of people are ready to pay 5000-20000 rupees for used products and 13% people ready to pay above 20000 rupees, because in Moodabidri area most of the people are from middle class they are facing financial problems.

The most of the people ready to purchase second hand products for 5000 – 20000 rupees.

Table no: 5. Annual family income.

Sl. No	Options	No of response	%
1	Below 15,000	5	9%
2	15,000-30,000	42	76%
3	30,000-50,000	7	13%
	Above 50,000	1	2%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that many people are having less income, 9% of people are earning below 15000 per annum, 76% of people are having 15,000-30,000 annual income and remaining 15% people earning above 30,000 per annum. Income of people effects on their purchase decision so in rural area marketing opportunity for second hand goods is more because rural people having less income. In rural area many people are having very less income per year so business opportunity for marketing of used products is more.

Table no: 6. Major problem in rural area.

Sl. No	Options	No of response	Percentage
1	Transportation problem	11	20%
2	Electricity problem	5	9%
3	Unemployment/ under employment	17	31%
4	Financial problem	13	27%
5	Communication network problem	9	16%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

The above table shows problems of rural people, 20% of people agreed that they are facing transportation problem, 9% of people facing electricity problem in some seasons, 31% of people facing unemployment or under employment problem, 27% of people agreed that they are facing financial problem and remaining 16% people facing communication network problem. The major problems in rural area are unemployment, financial, transportation and communication problems; there is not much difference between ratios of these problems.

Table no: 7 Main advertisement channel which effect on purchase decision.

Sl. No	Options	No of response	Percentage
1	Social media	13	24%
2	Wall printing	2	4%
3	TV	36	65%
4	Other	4	7%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

The above diagram shows that which advertisement media or channel attracts more in rural area, 24% respondents agreed that social media effects more on their purchasing decision, 4% respondents agreed that wall printing, 7% respondents agreed that other channels and 65% respondents agreed that TV advertisement effect on their purchase decision. In rural area TV advertisement is more effective compare to radio, social media, and wall printing and other modes of advertisement.

Table no: 8 Offer which changes purchase decision.

Sl. No	Options	No of response	Percentage
1	Cash back offer	5	9%
2	Warranty/ guarantee	13	24%
3	Discount	17	31%
4	Exchange offer	11	20%
5	Free service	9	16%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above table we can analyze which marketing strategy helps to attracts rural consumers, 9% respondents attracts to cash back offer, 24% respondents attracts to warranty and guarantee, 31% respondents agreed that discount attracts them on their purchasing decision, 20% respondents attracts to exchange offer and remaining 16% respondents attracts to Free service or services of seller. Every marketing strategy is attracting rural consumers.

Marketing strategies like warranty/guarantee, Discount, Exchange offer and service after the sales attracts most of the rural people, the ratios between these strategies are not having much difference.

Table no: 9 Famous second hand product marketing website in rural area

Sl. No	Options	No of response	Percentage
1	Quikr	18	33%
2	Ebay	6	11%
3	Olx	31	56%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

From the above table it is clearly explain that which online marketing website is famous in rural area, 56% of respondents mentioned that Olx is famous online marketing website, 33% people's

opinion that Quikr is famous and 11% respondents mentioned that Ebay online website is good and famous.

In rural area major 3 famous second hand goods marketing websites are Olx, Quikr and Ebay, these websites are having good image in rural area.

Table no: 10. Factor influences on purchase of second-hand goods.

Sl. No	Options	No of response	Percentage
1	Low income	21	38%
2	Non-availability of new product	3	5%
3	High price for new product (to save money)	31	56%
	Total	55	100%

Analysis and Interpretation:

The above table explains which factor or reason influences on purchase of used product. 38% people mentioned that because of low income they are purchasing second hand products, only 5% respondents agreed that because of non-availability of new products they are purchasing second hand products. 56% people purchasing used products because of high price for new product or to save money. People are not able to spent huge money on new products like electronic and automobile etc. Most of the people purchasing second-hand products because of high price for new products people tries to save money.

FINDINGS:

- Most of the respondents answered that quality of used products differ from new products so this leads to fear of purchasing used products.

- Infrastructure facilities in rural area are developing and literacy rate also increasing so online marketing opportunity is also more.
- It is clear from the research that the trend for second-hand buying will continue to rise. The main factor for purchasing used products by rural people is to save money.
- Many people selling their old products to marketers at very low price and some people donating their used products to poor people.
- Most of the poor and middle class people purchasing used products like auto mobile and white goods because of their financial problem or to save money.
- Students purchases secondhand books in rural area because they are not ready to pay high price for new books. Consumption of used products helps to save natural resources.
- Olx and Quikr are the two famous used products marketing websites in rural area but supply of fake brand is more in rural area..
- Television and social media are both effective advertisement channels, sometimes suggestion of retailer effect on purchasing decision of rural people.
- Second-hand products marketing websites like Olx, Quikr and Ebay are the most famous marketing websites in rural area.

SUGGESTIONS:

The concept of Rural Marketing in India Economy has always played an influential role in the lives of people. In India, leaving out a few metropolitan cities, all the districts and industrial townships are connected with rural markets. The rural market in India generates bigger revenues in the country as the rural regions comprise of the maximum consumers in this country. The rural market in Indian economy generates almost more than half of the country's income. Used product marketer is having good opportunity to expand his market in rural area, but he should undertake several strategies to attract rural people,

- Marketer should identify opportunity in rural area by researching needs of people, one need to identify the target group for each product; one need to analyze the purchasing power of the rural family.
- Focus on building trust with rural people rather than only focus on profit making.
- Marketer should focus on rural market through Promotional, Marketing strategies like target marketing, integrated marketing, emphasis on consumer satisfaction to achieve his objectives and to make business in rural areas.
- Develop an appropriate distribution strategies like indirect, direct, Intensive, selective, exclusive strategies.
- The one who planning to enter the rural market should identify the areas where he can provide best services to satisfy needs of rural customers.
- Needs to have a regular update of the rural market products which need ordering; update of which rural market products are most in demand and popular; information about which product is popular in which age group.

CONCLUSION

In market there are several difficulties confronting the effort to fully explore the rural markets. The concept of rural markets in India is still in evolving shape, and the marketers facing variety of challenges. Many successful brands have shown high note of failure in the rural

markets because the marketers try to extend marketing plans that they use in urban areas. The unique consumption pattern, tastes, and need of the rural consumers should be analyzed at the product planning stage so that they match the needs of the rural people.

In rural area agriculture is first and also the main source of income. Income is seasonal in nature and fluctuates as it depends on crop production. Marketer is having good opportunity to start his business because of increasing in people's income, literacy rate and standard of living. Rural marketing helps to balance industrial growth, improve rural infrastructures, easy marketability of agricultural produces, optimum utilization of rural untapped resources, employment generation, marketing acts as catalyst agent for economic growth. Used products marketing is profitable for individuals and consumption of used product saves natural resources and helps to sustainable development. In modern economy there is a more demand for used products, therefore marketing of used product is good business opportunity.

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A STUDY ON BUYING BEHAVIOR OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS AMONG UNDERGRADUATE LEVEL FEMALE STUDENTS WITH REFERENCE TO BELTHANGADY TALUK OF DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT.

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ABSTRACT

From the ancient literature to present all poets, writers have been symbolizing beauty to women. Beauty has been matter of concern and is the main subject to market any product for the marketer, in any advertisements, whether related or not marketers cast women as a symbol of beauty Majority of the women are beauty conscious when comparing to men they have got highly sensitive and soft skin, all females tend to purchase and use cosmetics either to safeguard their sensitive skin or to look beautiful. When we compare cities with rural areas cities are much smarter with all infrastructure facilities but rural areas are lagging behind so the people are. Buying behavior changes from one person to another because of difference in personal stimuli, perception and other factors. In cities people can get goods of their choice with ease but this is not so in the case of rural areas especially when they are lacking in transportation facility and network connectivity. Majority of the rural females are daily wage workers who work in either in the paddy fields or Areca estates. This paper is an outcome of an attempt made to know about the buying behavior of the undergraduate level rural female students of belthangady taluk while purchasing the cosmetic products, paper also highlights opportunities for the marketers to serve better and scope for entrepreneurship.

Key words: - Rural female students, opportunities for the marketers, entrepreneurship

INTRODUCTION

From the ancient literature to present all poets, writers have been symbolizing women to beauty. Beauty has been a matter of concern and is the main subject for to the market any product to the marketers in any advertisements whether related or not marketers cast women as a symbol of beauty.

Majority of the women are beauty conscious. When comparing to men they have got highly sensitive and soft skin, all females tend to purchase and use cosmetics either to safeguard their sensitive skin or to look beautiful. When we compare cities with rural areas cities are much smarter with all infrastructure but rural areas are lagging behind so the people are. The cost of living in rural area is much less than the cities and rural people will have a different consumption pattern, priorities because of connectivity and other socio economic causes.

Every individual is having urge or desire or stimuli, when a certain offering matches with his desire or urge or stimuli it creates demand. And certain set of activities shown by him in satisfying his stimuli or urge collectively called as buying behavior.”¹ behavior is the total response which man makes to the situations in life with which either is confronted”.

A buying behavior is the behavior shown by the consumer or customer while prioritizing the product or shop. There are two types of buying behavior.

1. Buying behavior shown on purchasing the particular product with reference to other products.
2. Buying behavior shown in preferring one particular shop with reference to other shops.

Both above types of buying behaviors are influenced by various factors such as

- a) Price
- b) Product packaging and way of display in shops
- c) Impact of salesmen
- d) Offers and discounts
- e) Quality of the product and good will of the shops
- f) Buyers personal beliefs
- g) Distance of shops
- h) Availability of products etc.,

Because of easy accessibility to social media, growing peer group circle through whats app and other “friendly apps” the youth of rural areas have been modernizing themselves. Nowadays they quickly adapt to modern trends. This paper is an outcome of an attempt made to know about the buying behavior depicted in purchasing cosmetics by undergraduate level students who falling from rural areas of belthangady taluk of Dakshina kannada district.

OBJECTIVES:

- To know about the buying behavior of female undergraduate students with respect of cosmetic products.
- To know about consumption pattern
- To know about brand preference
- To know about satisfaction level
- To know about easy availability of cosmetic products in rural areas

STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

Majority of the respondents are from the rural and from economically weaker sections, where the male and female senior members of the families are involved as coolie either in paddy fields or in areca estates. Since they are from rural area from economically weaker sections authors have

made an attempt to know about their buying behavior with respect of cosmetics and expenditure pattern on them.

METHODOLOGY

Based on the requirements of the study, data is collected from secondary sources such as published books, online PDF files reports of various authors and at the same time by structured questionnaire method. 63 samples were collected through Google form with structured set of questions. Convenient method of non-random sampling is followed to meet the objectives of the study in belthangady region.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

MRS. J. VIDHYA JAWAHAR AND DR. K. TAMZHJYOTHI (2013) held in their study “consumer attitude towards cosmetic products” that middle aged people have positive attitude towards cosmetic products compared to young aged people to keep themselves young or to give young appearance. And family income won't effect upon the attitudes towards beauty cosmetic products.

DR. M.SHAJAHANAN AND DR. S. MOHAMMED SAFI (2019) in their study on consumer behavior with respect of cosmetic products in tiruchirappalli district held that consumers will buy products by observing products through TV and they buy from fancy stores for every 15 days.

SCHIFMAN, KANUK (2009) consumers who had no experience with a product will trust well known brand name. Consumers think that well known brands are better and are worth buying for implied assurance of quality dependability, performance and service.

KOTLER (2004) because of difference in human psychology, demographical difference and age and sex every consumer exhibits different approaches while buying and in some situations consumer's selection and choice is influenced by the family.

GEOGRAPHIC AND DEMOGRAPHIC VIEW OF BELTHANGADY TALUK²

Belthangady taluk is mostly covered by forests and hills of Western Ghats. This taluk has an average elevation of 685 meters (2247 feet) it covers an area of 1375 square kilometers.

As per 2001 census, belthangady taluk had a population of 2, 46,494 with 1, 21,288 males (49.2%) and 1,25,206 females (50.8%) the taluk is covered with 02.9% urban area and 97.1% in rural area.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

PART – A Table.1: profile of the respondents

Particulars	No. of respondents		Percentage
Total number of respondents	63		100
Graduation stream	B.A	20	31.74
	B.COM	25	40.00

	B.C.A	13	20.63
	BNSY	03	04.76
	BPED	02	03.17
	Total	63	

The PART –A consist of basic information of the respondents. Data is collected from total 63 female respondents who are studying in undergraduate colleges of Belthangady taluk. It is also evident that majority of the respondents are from traditional courses.

PART –B Table 1: frequency of purchasing cosmetic products

Frequency	No. of respondents	Percentage
Rarely	34	53.96
Frequently	14	22.22
Very rarely	15	23.81
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above data it is clear that more than 50% of the respondents are purchasing the product rarely and very rarely(total together 77.67%). As respondents are young and they falling from rural background further their economic condition also have influence over purchase frequency.

Table 2: type of cosmetic product used

Product	No. of respondents	Percentage
Powder+ eyeliner+ lipstick	38	60.31
Only eyeliner	04	6.34
Only lipstick	03	4.76
Only powder	11	17.47
Any other	07	11.11
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above table it is clear that respondents prefer to buy combo packs. 60.31% of the respondents purchase three products together. Marketers will have a better market if they market in combos. It is evident that there is less demand for single product.

Table 3: purpose of using cosmetics

Purpose	No. of respondents	Percentage
Facial care	28	44.44
Young looks	08	12.69
Improving self image	22	34.92
To look attractive to others	05	7.94
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

Majority of the respondents use cosmetics for facial care (44.44%), as they are young they won't use to look young only minute percentage use cosmetics to look young. And 34.92% of the respondents use to improve self image and 7.94% uses to look attractive to others. There is much scope for facial care products such as face washes etc.,

Table 4: brand preference of the respondents

Brand	No. of respondents	Percentage
Lakme	23	36.50
ponds	13	20.63
Dazzler	18	28.57
Any other	09	14.29
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

Majority of the respondents prefer lakme products over other products and 28.57% of people prefer dazzler product. And 20.63% of people use ponds .This is because these are the very popular brands in the locality because of their quality.

Table 5: factor influencing selection of cosmetic brand

Factors	No. of respondents	Percentage
Peer group influence	04	6.34
Quality	47	74.60
Advertisements	05	7.94
Ingredients	07	11.11
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above table it is clear that more than 50% (74.60%) of the respondents seek quality while selecting the cosmetic brand, there is less influence of peer groups and advertisements.

Table 6: factor influencing selection of product

Factors	No. of respondents	Percentage
Features and quality	37	58.73
Brand	12	19.05
Price	10	15.87
Discounts	04	6.35
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above table it is clear that more than 50% of the respondents seek quality in products over other characteristics such as brand price and discounts.

Table 7: purchase of cosmetics from

Preference	No. of respondents	Percentage
General stores	32	50.79
Medical shops	26	41.27
Fancy shops	01	1.59
Online shopping	04	6.35
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

As the respondents are falling from rural background they don't have Access to sophisticated specialized shops and majority of the respondents purchase cosmetics from local general stores (50.79%) and medical shops (41.27%). And there is very less number for fancy shops and online shopping.

Table 8: influence of sales men or beautician over purchase

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	23	36.50
No	35	55.55
May be	05	7.94
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

It is observed that along with quality consideration near about 36% of respondents also influenced by salesmen and beautician over their purchase and 55% of respondents responded negatively. And 7% of respondents are not in the position to decide whether they are influenced or not.

Table 9: patronizing beauty parlor

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	21	33.33
No	42	66.66
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above data it is clear that majority of the respondents are not frequent to beautify parlors this so because there is difficulty in accessing parlors. Parlors are situated in urban areas of rural areas so there is no easy access. People have to come to urban areas for the beauty parlors and there are no timely transportation facilities and this fact creates opportunities for self employment in this field.

Table 10: Easy Availability of Cosmetics

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	33	52.38
No	30	47.61
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

As the respondents are residing in rural areas the availability of cosmetic products is less. The local shop keepers more concentrate on daily and essential needs of the customers and they keep products accordingly, near about 47.61% of the respondents responded negatively.

Table 11: Monthly expenditure on cosmetics

Amount	No. of respondents	Percentage
100 -200	35	55.55
500-1000	13	20.63
1000 and above	05	07.94
Depends on the product	10	15.87
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the table above it is clear that near about 55.55% of respondents spend below 200 Rs on cosmetics and there are less number of respondents who like to spend high priced products.

FINDINGS

- ❖ From the study we found out that majority of the female students rarely purchase cosmetics. May be because of non-availability products or may be because of economic background the study has limitation in these areas.
- ❖ It was found that majority of the respondents are having concern towards facial skin and about to improve self-image marketer can consider these factors to market better.
- ❖ It was found that respondents prefer only popular products and they consider quality while purchasing product and in selection of brand.
- ❖ It is observed that respondents have purchased from general stores and medical shops than fancy and online shopping.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents are not frequent to beauty parlors may be because of less number of parlors or improper transport services in rural areas this study has limitation in these aspects.
- ❖ There is improper supply of cosmetics and are not easily available in the rural areas and the majority of the respondents used to spend below 200 Rs.

CONCLUSION:

Human behavior is not programmed like any computer, human beings are of all senses and they show different behavior at different situations. Social media, technological growth made everybody smart even today's kid knows better than older generation with respect of technology. But growth in technology, social Medias made less impact on the buying behavior of cosmetics in rural areas. Only qualitative products and those products which are available easily in the locality at low price are preferred, further there are ample opportunities for the female individuals for the self-employment in the rural areas as they can start a business as a beautician.

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UNDERSTANDING THE PERCEPTION OF CONSUMERS' REGARDING OBSTACLES ON DIGITAL PAYMENT SYSTEM (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UDUPI AND DAKSHINA KANNADA REGION

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ABSTRACT

Today consumer behaviour has become the central topic of marketing because consumer is the king of the marketing. As everywhere technological changes are taking place in the modern world, there is a change/advancement even in method of payment. But consumers should be aware about this advancement in method of payment because if lack of awareness then it leads the consumer to hesitate/resist digital payment system. So there is a need of consumer education on digital services which supports the adoption of digital modes of payments. This paper makes an attempt to understand the consumers' perception and behaviour towards digital payment services and also tries to identify the causes of user's resistance. This research paper focuses on the perception and attitude of consumers of Udupi and Dakshina Kannada region regarding obstacles on digital payment system. The data is collected both from primary and secondary sources. Around 1,000 samples were taken in Udupi and Dakshina Kannada region for this survey. The variables that influence the consumer's to adopt to electronic payments services are identified to analyze the impact of digital payments.

Keywords: Digital payments, consumers, demonetization, consumers' education, digital security.

1. INTRODUCTION

The need for improving the trends of digital payments system is very important to make a transparency in all the transactions. In India to promote the digital payment system, Government started a campaign called the Digital India. As part of promoting cashless business and converting India into less-cash culture, various modes of digital payments are made available like internet banking, mobile wallets, banking card, USSD, UPI, AEPS, banks pre-paid cards, point of sale, mobile banking, micro ATMs, etc. Digital payment system is completely based on the modern technology which includes electronic means and internet. So the marketers need to understand and cater for a wide variety of consumers' segments. Time and experience is needed for customers to adjust to new types of risks associated with digital payment. Due to

unawareness, lack of education, lack of trust (fear on security for their money), perceived difficulties of use, language problem, web server problem, lack of computer literacy, the consumers are resistant to adopt digital payment services most the time. So it is necessary to arrange some programmes on digital payment system to educate the consumers.

2. OBJECTIVES

- 1) To understand the Perception of consumers' regarding obstacles on digital payments.
- 2) To study the difficulties faced by consumers in using digital services.
- 3) To analyse the reasons behind the problems faced by the consumers.
- 4) To identify the solutions for the problem faced.

3. METHODOLOGY

The resources collected to prepare this paper were both from primary and secondary data.

PRIMARY DATA

Primary data were collected through survey by distributing questionnaires to 100 students of various colleges in Udupi and Dakshina Kannada region. Simple percentage analysis has been done to evaluate the data.

SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data collected with the help of various books, newspapers, journals, internet and some online thesis and magazines etc.

4. ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this questionnaire is to find out the opinion of few consumers' of Udupi and Dakshina Kannada region about digital payment system.

4.1 Do you have knowledge on Digital Payment System?

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	450	45%
No	550	55%
Total	1000	100%

Interpretation: Out of 1000 consumers only 450 respondents were having knowledge on Digital Payment System.

4.2 How do you get to know the knowledge about Digital Payment System?

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Through Friends	100	10%
Social Media	420	42%
Through Advertisements	100	10%
Through Bank	380	38%
Total	1000	100%

Interpretation: Out of 1000 respondents only 380 consumers got the awareness about Digital Payment system from Bank.

4.3 How many times have you done digital transaction before?

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Only Once	200	20%
Two	250	25%
Three	250	25%
More than Four	300	30%
Total	1000	100%

Interpretation: Out of 1000 respondents an around 20% of consumers have not used digital payment system much.

4.4 What is your perception towards digital payment system?

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Trustworthy	400	40%
Untrustworthy	600	60%
Total	1000	100%

Interpretation: Out of 1000 respondents 48% of consumers are still worried about digital payment system.

4.5 Level of agreement to the following questions.

Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I think Digital Payment System is Risky.	500	160	040	150	150
Digital Payment System is difficult.	400	080	230	180	110
I prefer to withdraw money from bank	500	040	150	120	190
Digital Payment System is safe.	150	150	150	200	350
I think digital payment is better substitute for traditional cash payment system	380	180	130	110	200
Digital Payment is cost saving	300	100	320	150	130
Digital Payment is not time consuming	300	070	100	220	310
More guidance from the educational institutions, banks and Government regarding this is required.	480	280	40	130	070

Interpretation:

- ▶ Around 50% of consumers agree that digital payment system is risky.
- ▶ 40% of consumers feel that digital payment system is difficult.
- ▶ 50% of consumers strongly like to withdraw the money from bank.
- ▶ Only 15% of consumers are stated that digital payment system is safe.
- ▶ Around 38% of consumers think that online banking is better substitute for traditional banking system.
- ▶ 30% of consumers have strongly stated that digital payment is not costly.
- ▶ 30% of consumers strongly believe that digital payment system saves the time.
- ▶ 38% of consumers are strongly agreed that more participation of education institutions, banks regarding encouragement, support, motivation, and in giving information about digital payment is required.

5. FINDINGS

- 1) Out of 1000 consumers only 450 consumers were thought about digital payment system. Remaining 550 consumers are not interested in that.
- 2) Out of 1000 respondents only 380 consumers got the awareness about digital payment system from the bank. Through friends 100 consumers, through advertisements 100. But majority of the consumers responded that they got the information about the digital payment system from social media.
- 3) Out of 1000, 300 consumers have used more than four times digital transaction before.
- 4) 500 consumers strongly agree that digital payment system is risky. 160 consumers support to this statement. Whereas 40 consumers are in dilemma. 300 consumers are disagreeing with this.
- 5) 400 consumers strongly feel that digital payment system is difficult. 80 consumers support for this. 230 consumers are there in both the sides. Whereas 390 consumers feel that digital payment system is not difficult.
- 6) Out of 1000 respondents 50% of consumers like to make cash payment. It clearly indicates that still they feel comfortable with traditional banking system.
- 7) 30% of consumers realised that digital payment system saves the time. It means for rest of them still awareness is required.
- 8) 48% of respondents strongly say that they need guidance from educational institutions and banks regarding digital payment system. It means they are interested to learn new system.

6. SUGGESTIONS

The need for improving the trends of digital payments system in India is very important. But changing consumer behavior takes many years. From the finding it clearly indicates that still most of the consumers want traditional method of payment because of unawareness, lack of education, perceived difficulties of use, language problem, web server problem, lack of computer literacy, the consumers are resistant to adopt digital payment services. And moreover they are scared enough to use digital payment system this is because of lack of trust (fear on security for their money). Managing information security is a very complex issue. But the future of digital payment system is secure due to increasing adoption and arrival of new technologies to address

existing limitations. So the banks must educate people about net banking services provided by their respective banks to their customer while opening the account. For that banks should identify reasons for resistance and guide them properly by proper marketing campaigns, communication with customers, customer training, providing user friendly website design and the banks must make their customers feel safer by providing more security other than OTP. Government should provide necessary infrastructure facilities for the effective implementation of digital payments plans. As digital payment methods are based on cards, mobile apps and internet and it needs technical knowledge, even Government needs to arrange more awareness programs to make the people to know the terms related to digital India. It is found through the study that only some of the consumers go for digital payment. So trainings programs must be taken up in schools, colleges and Universities, Conferences, Seminar and workshops are required to be organized to discuss and create awareness about the various payments methods and new technologies and the benefits of digital payment services among customers.

7. LIMITATIONS

The sample size for this study is based on the availability of respondents in the target group, which could be a limitation in generalizing the result of findings. Therefore, a similar empirical finding with a wider sample size will be necessary in order to determine the generalised conclusion about rural people participation.

8. CONCLUSION

The most recent technological advancement is the evolution of Digital Payment System. Slowly India is moving from cash to less-cash economy. But still it has not been accepted by all the customers. The reasons may be lack of trust, lack of technical knowledge, fear of traceability of transaction, habit, unawareness, lack of education, perceived difficulties of use, language problem, web server problem, lack of computer literacy, etc. It is found through the study that only some of the customers use digital payment system. So Youth centered trainings programs must be taken up in schools, colleges and Universities, Conferences, Seminar and workshops are required to be organized to discuss and create awareness about the various payments methods and new technologies among customers by the Government, education institutions, and banks. If awareness is created on customers towards digital payment system so that they will encourage the future generation too.

9. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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10. DECLARATION

We do here by declare that it is the original work, and the paper has neither been published/presented nor sent for publication anywhere else.

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ROLE OF ACTION RESEARCH IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF SELF AWARENESS IN TEACHING AMONG B.ED., TRAINEES.

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ABSTRACT

Teaching and Research are the two faces of the same coin. Teaching is the practical part of the Research. Teaching plays the role of education and Action Research plays the role of the Philosophy. Research in any discipline dives deep into the ocean of knowledge to discover new relations, new theories and better understanding of various phenomenons. Besides the basic role of creating of fund of knowledge, research also acts as an agent of change and improvement. Every teacher becomes a researcher to the extent that he or she perceives the problem, designs an Action Research Project, experiments to test the hypothesis and finally comes out with solution, to improve teaching and there by enhance the learning on the part of learners. As the name suggests, Action Research is the methodology which has the dual aims of action and research. In the present 2 year B.Ed., programme one of the areas of training is the school internship. One of the components is the class room based Research Project where the student trainee should undergo Action Research. This programme provides the plat form for the interns to give expression to their learning while planning and reflecting on their own experience. In present paper study on Action Research of the B.Ed., trainees are explained. The tool Self awareness in teaching was used to collect the data. Simple Statistics technique was used to analysis and interpretation of the data. The study revealed that the Action Research improved the self-awareness in teaching among the trainees.

INTRODUCTION:-

It is the one of the types of the Research, most of the times considered as methodology which has the dual aims of action and Research.

“Action research concentrate on immediate application but not in development of theory.”

Kulbir singh siddu.

The Action researches start with intention or planning before action and review or critique after. The following figure depict the Action research cycle

What out comes do i wish to Achieve?

PLAN

What action do i think will achieve the out come?

ACTION

Did i achieve the desired out comes?

Steps of the Action Research:-The steps of the Action Research are as like the Research ,But there is no any strict and rigid steps as such.

1. Identification of the problem.
2. Analysis of the problem to define and delimit it.
3. Diagnosing the factors causing the problem.
4. Formulating action hypothesis.
5. Designing the action plan
6. Collection of data and analysis/Evaluation of action hypothesis.
7. Research report writing.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY.

1. To explore the improvement in teaching skill among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees
2. To explore the improvement in self-awareness in teaching among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees.
3. To check the level of knowledge about the Action research among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees.
4. To study the ability of analyzing and interpretation of data Through Action research among B.Ed., Teacher trainees.

5. To study the intention of application of Action research to improve their own abilities among the B.Ed., trainees.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY.

1. There is no significant improvement in teaching skill among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees through the Action Research.

2. There is no significant improvement in self awareness in teaching among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees through Action Research.

3. There is no good level of knowledge about the Action research among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees.

4. There is no ability of analyzing and interpretation of data through Action Research is developed among B.Ed.,

5. There is no intention of application of Action research to improve their own abilities among the B.Ed., trainees.

METHODOLOGY.

Method adopted. The investigator used normative survey method for collection of data.

SAMPLE.

The sample selected includes 50 2nd year B.Ed., trainees from Ballari B.Ed., colleges by using the stratified sampling technique.

TOOLS.

The investigator prepared a self awareness in teaching scale consists of 15 questions which are rated using 3point scale namely to a great extent, to some extent, not at all. Percentage analysis was done to analyze the responses of student trainees.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA.

Table 1- Responses of B.Ed., trainees on self awareness in teaching through Action Research.

SL No	Test Item	To great extent (%)	To some extent (%)	Not at all(%)
01	Action Research is very simple.	44(88)	6(12)	0(0)
02	Action Research consumes more time.	4(8)	14(28)	32(64)
03	The Researcher is the consumer in Action Research.	46(92)	4(8)	0(0)
04	Action Research develops self awareness in teaching in a teacher.	45(90)	3(6)	2(4)
05	Action Research can be taken by any professionals.	42(84)	4(8)	4(8)
06	Action Research is good for the beginners that	41(82)	5(10)	4(8)

	to student teachers.			
07	Application of simple statistics in Action Research improves the analysis and synthesis ability in teacher trainee.	39(78)	8(16)	3(6)
08	Planning of proper educational and learning experiences is possible to teacher through the Action research plan in Action Research	45(90)	4(8)	1(2)
09	Action Research improves the teaching skills of teacher and hence the ability of understanding among learners.	47(94)	1(2)	2(4)
10	Action Research is not burden to teacher it is a part of the teaching.	33(66)	14(28)	3(6)
11	Action is the main aim of Action Research and Research is the fringe benefit of the Action.	44(88)	2(4)	4(8)
12	The aim of the Action Research is planning and execution of the proper actions not formulation of the theory.	48(96)	2(4)	0(0)
13	Outcomes of Action Research results can be extended to other teachers and generalize.	28(56)	15(30)	7(14)
14	The teacher training colleges can be document the Action Research of student trainees.	48(96)	2(4)	0(0)
15	Publication as “What research says to the class room teacher” may also publish and circulate widely.	34(68)	10(20)	6(12)

Table 1 reveals that 88% of trainees supports that Action Research is simple. But 78.5% of trainees felt that Action Research is burden and at the same time 66% trainees support that Action Research is a part of teaching, It shows that trainees are in confusion about the part of teaching and extra work. 68% trainees support the publication and wide circulation of Action Research. The statement Action is important and Research is the fringe benefit of it is accepted by 96% trainees. Action Research is develops self-awareness is supported by 90% trainees.

So the hypothesis 1 to 5 are rejected the directive Hypothesis are accepted.

Conclusion.

“Think well is wise, Planning well is wiser, Doing well is wisest” is the Persian proverb is suitable for the Action Research. It is primarily quantitative hence more responsive to situation. So strengthening the Action Research in teacher training will improve the ability of teachers and hence quality of the education. Action Research often emphasizes local relevance (that is responsive) at the cost of global relevance (that is generalization). When change is one of the intended outcomes the training colleges should adopt practice the Action Research among the trainees.

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PERCEPTION AND EXPERIENCE OF USERS ON MOOC'S SWAYAM - A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS' OF BELTHANGADY TALUK

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ABSTRACT:

Online learning uses technology for delivering the courses. Education with technology is considered as the most promising development in education. With technology globalization, the concept of learning and teaching has undergone a tremendous change. Technological usage in education provides a global learning environment, which allows accessing the course material anytime, anywhere, connect other learners, and get access to the content without considering any geographical boundaries. The significant changes in the use of technology in online education have seen the emergence of the concept of Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). SWAYAM platform is indigenously developed by Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) and All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) with the help of Microsoft and would be ultimately capable of hosting 2000 courses and 80000 hours of learning: covering school, under-graduate, post-graduate, engineering, law and other professional courses. University Grants Commission (UGC) has vided Gazette Notification dated 19 th July 2016, notified Regulation, 2016 regarding 'Credit Framework for Online Learning Courses through SWAYAM'. SWAYAM has been developed under four-quadrant approaches: (1) video lecture, (2) specially prepared reading material that can be downloaded/printed (3) self-assessment tests through tests and quizzes and (4) an online discussion forum for clearing the doubts.SWAYAM is an indigenous (Made in India) IT Platform for hosting the Massive Open Online Courses. The study is conducted among the Postgraduate students of Belthangady taluk to know the experience of users and to know the various challenges faced by the students while accessing the various courses.

KEYWORDS: Mooc's – Swayam, Higher education, Digital learning, Technology, Online course

INTRODUCTION

Education is the foundation for a successful life; it is a powerful weapon which can help one change the world. The Indian higher education system is one of the oldest and largest in the world with 917 universities including Institutions of National Importance, more than 45,000 colleges, 3.66 crore students and 12.84 lakh, teachers. This massification of higher education brings along with it many issues which confront the higher education of our country today like, the issues of access, equity, relevance, quality, management and financing.

The world is going digital, so should our learning. The phenomenal growth of ICT in the education system has had a tremendous impact globally. India has been quick enough to leverage technology for teaching-learning processes as ICT has facilitated the accessibility to education and promoting quality teaching and learning to learners of all age groups across the length and breadth of the country. Taking cognizance of such advancements, The Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India launched SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds), an indigenously developed platform aimed at providing learning opportunities to the learners through MOOCs (Massive Open Online Course) free of cost in a structured manner¹.

The MOOCs on the SWAYAM are high quality, curriculum-based, interactive content in different subjects across disciplines of social sciences, arts, fine arts, humanities, natural & mathematical sciences, linguistics, languages, technology, management, teacher training and skill sector². These courses are developed by the best faculty of the country carefully chosen from various educational institutions across the country from Secondary till Post-Graduation level. The basic philosophy of MOOCs on SWAYAM is free learning for anyone, anytime, Anywhere (AAA) with the facility of credit transfer for up to 20% of the courses in a programme. Although this programme is in the initial stage under the Mangalore university affiliated colleges. There may be a lot of problems and confusion among the student community and much more expectation towards the project so; the study is conducted in the Belthangady taluk to ascertain the experience of the postgraduate students, who are already enrolled under MOOC's SWAYAM.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- ❖ To know the satisfaction level about SWAYAM course among the graduate students
- ❖ To find out the various problems faced while accessing the course.
- ❖ To know the expectations of the users regarding the Swayam platform.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

According to **Kaveri et al. (2016)**, “The strength of SWAYAM lies in its qualitative evaluation systems as well as recognition of credits, equity of access and affordability. Traditional HEIs have a clear edge over global MOOCs and SWAYAM in terms of long term impact on citizen and society building and shaping individual opinions”.

Kanjilal (2016), “Mainstreaming the SWAYAM initiative with the formal education system will go a long way in realizing the dream of the nation in universal access of education. With appropriate planning and implementation, SWAYAM can play a pivotal role in Digital India and Skill India missions of the government of India”.

According to **Bharti (2014)**, "SWAYAM is a platform for new India where quality education is affordable and self-learning is fruitful not only for enrolled but also for professionals and dropouts. With quality content, best online lectures, great discussions, and knowledgeable

assessment quizzes, SWAYAM will provide a great opportunity to Indian students to learn without fearing from failure.”

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

As per the New Higher Education policy, the Government is planning to render the education based on equity, quality, and relevance and to promote the Life-Long Learning. The MHRD department has come up with the new platform called SWAYAM, where learners can choose from hundreds of course and every course is taught by the best teacher of various prestigious Institutions. As per the new education policy, 2019 proposed by the government gives special importance to the MOOC's course and the SWAYAM platform. Although this programme is in beginning stage, there is a lack of knowledge among the students' communities and academicians, on the same even though there are students who have already enrolled for the courses under SWAYAM website. The study is mainly based on those enrolled students to know the experience of the usage, problems and expectations regarding the online courses.

METHODOLOGY:

The paper employed a survey method to acquire information regarding the students' experience with MOOC's SWAYAM. The target of the study is in Belthangady Taluk. The samples are students from different colleges. In an online survey, 43 students have responded to the study. The non-random sampling method is used. To provide the theoretical background and strengthen the discussion books and the journals were referred. The collected data is presented in the form of tables.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS OF DATA COLLECTED FROM THE ONLINE SURVEY:

Table 1: Period of Usage

Duration	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
One month	34	79
One year	07	16
More than a year	02	05
TOTAL	43	100

Source: Survey

From the above table, it is clear that out of 43 respondents 34 are using the platform from last one month because the colleges are recently giving much importance towards the SWAYAM initiative. 7 respondents are using since one year and rest 02 respondents using from more than a year. This shows that students are coming to know about the programme very recently and they are enrolled under the same.

Table .2: Acquiring the use pattern of SWAYAM

Use pattern	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Personal effort	04	09
Lecturers	22	51
Library staffs	09	21

Orientation	08	19
TOTAL	43	100

Source: Survey

The table shows the information regarding the source of awareness regarding the SWAYAM among the users. It is clear that 51% of the respondents are come to know about SWAYAM through their lecturers and 21% from the library staff and 19% respondents opine that through orientation they got the idea, here we can understand that the lecturers are encouraging the students towards the online courses.

Table .3: Reasons for usage

Reasons	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Different kind of courses	23	53
Anytime learning	08	19
Experience Faculty	05	12
Video/Audio / Pdf content	06	14
TOTAL	43	100

Source: Survey

The above data clearly shows that the various reasons to use SWAYAM platform by the respondents. 53% of respondents opine that there is the availability of a large number of courses so the students can opt any of the interested courses without any regulations. 19% of respondents are opined that it facilitates any time learning without the four walls and chalk and talk system. 12% feels that the platform has experienced faculty and 14% says the course method is good.

Table 4: College under Swayam Local chapter

Opinion	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	17	40
No	26	60
TOTAL	43	100

Source: Survey

From the table, it is clear that only 40% of Respondents College is in the SWAYAM Local Chapter list that means they get all the information in an up to date manner. Remaining 60% of the respondent's college is not in the SWAYAM local chapter list.

Table 5: Duration of time spent

Duration	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Daily	05	12
Weekly	29	68
Once in a two days	08	19
TOTAL	43	100

Source: Survey

The above table deals with the duration of time spent for a particular course by the users.68% respondents weekly went through the topics and submit the assignments whereas 19% of the

respondents are accessing the once in two days and only 12% of the students are daily go through the course and read related topics.

Table .6: Problems while accessing the course

Reasons	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
App breakdown	11	26
Difficult interface	17	40
Connectivity issues	09	20
Registration/ login	06	14
TOTAL	43	100

Source: Survey

From the table, it is clear that respondents face various problems while accessing the SWAYAM platform through App or Website. 40% of the respondents state that there is a difficult interface and it is difficult to surf the various courses. 26% of the respondents face the problem of breakdowns of website and app. 20% of the respondents face connectivity issues and rest 14% of the respondents face the problem of registration/login.

Table 7: Satisfaction level of Users

Opinion	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	31	72
No	12	28
TOTAL	43	100

Source: Survey

The table shows the satisfaction level of users, in the above table, it is clear that 72% of the respondents are satisfied with interface and courses offered by the SWAYAM website, whereas 28% of the respondents are not satisfied with the platform.

Table .7.1: If No. Specify the Reasons

Reasons	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
High fee structure	05	42
Low connectivity	02	17
Exam centres	03	25
Confusions regarding start/end date	02	16
TOTAL	12	100

Source: Survey

The above table clears that the various reasons for the dissatisfaction, out of 12 dissatisfied respondents 5 respondents opine that they have to pay high charges for the certificate and it is not affordable in the rural area colleges. 3 respondents say that they have to travel a long distance to write the exams and the rest of the respondents gives the reasons of low connectivity and confusions over the course.

Table .8: Expectations of the users regarding SWAYAM

Reasons	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Nominal charges	13	30
Web-based examination	04	09
Easy Search Interface	05	12
More Orientation	21	49
TOTAL	43	100

Source: Survey

The table indicates the various expectations by the users regarding the Swayam. 49% of the respondents believe that there is a need for more orientation regarding the same, 30% of respondents expect the lower charges for the examination and certificate. 12% and 9% of the respondents opined that the website should use easy interface and it should conduct the web-based examinations.

FINDINGS:

- ❖ From the study, we found that 79% of the respondents are using and enrolled for the course under SWAYAM platform because of the continuous orientation and encouragement by the lecturers and institutions.
- ❖ The study clearly shows that 51% of the respondents came to know about online courses under Swayam from their lecturers whereas others from the library staffs and through orientations.
- ❖ Among the respondents 53% use the website/app because they get plenty of courses in different areas, 19% of respondents opine that it facilitates any time anywhere learning.
- ❖ From the study, we found that 60% of Respondents College is not in the Swayam local chapter list that means out of 3 colleges in the belthangady taluk only one college which is enrolled under Local chapter.
- ❖ The study clears that 68% of the respondents are accessing the course on a weekly basis; they study the content and submit the assignments per week.
- ❖ We found from the study that 40% of the respondents face the problem of a difficult interface, whereas 26% were facing the problem of breakdowns rest 34% face the problem while login.
- ❖ The study reveals that 28% of the respondents are not satisfied with MOOC's Swayam because of the high fee structure for examination, unavailability of exam centres and confusions over start and end of the course.
- ❖ From the study, it is clear that 49% of the respondents expect an orientation in the part of usage and regarding the courses, whereas 30% expect to decrease the fees for the examination.

SUGGESTIONS:

- ✓ The respective departments of MHRD and educational institutions need to provide more orientation to the student community and also should advertise the course in the social and print media.
- ✓ The website and app of SWAYAM should be redesign in such a manner that the users may not find any difficulties while surfing the courses and other course-related information.

- ✓ The examination charge should be kept nominal so that the students from rural colleges can afford and also the colleges should enrol themselves in the local chapters so that they can apply for the fee waiving facility.

CONCLUSION:

The MOOCs are the future of today's distance learning. They have made the education easily accessible to anyone anywhere anytime around the globe and made people's life more improved by providing flexible and quality learning as it was earlier. They have made a difference by providing free courses and enabled people and students' world around to participate, interact, discuss and learn from the renowned faculty of this world thereby improving people's lives and bring out the real change to communities as a whole. As per the UGC guidelines, the colleges now started to encourage the students towards the online courses, though the students are aware of the platform still various technical problems create difficulties to the users so the respected stakeholder needs to improve the quality and interface of the SWAYAM platform.

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A STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING THE IMPULSE BUYING BEHAVIOR AMONG YOUNG WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses in understanding the factors influencing the impulse buying behavior among young women. In this study a survey was conducted among women between the age group of 18 to 25 years. The study is based on primary data collected through questionnaires and also secondary data collected from books journals and the internet. Impulsive buying behavior is better understood by examining the impulsive buying tendency that shapes such behaviors. Due to globalization the younger generations now have easy access in purchasing a wide variety of goods or products. Apart from this there are wide varieties of psychological/social as well as marketing factors that pushes impulsive buying.

Hence this study is made to find out more regarding such factors that pushes young women into impulsive buying.

Keywords: impulse buying, buying behaviors, women buyers, psychological factors

INTRODUCTION

An impulse purchase or impulse buy is an unplanned decision to buy a product or service made just before taking a buying decision. The one who makes purchase is called as an impulse buyer or the impulse researcher. Research findings have concluded that emotions and feelings play a huge role in purchasing and is triggered by seeing the product or at times at the exposure to a well-crafted promotional message. Impulse buying disturbs the regular buying pattern or the normal buying decision. The regular or logical sequence of the consumer's action is replaced with an irrational moment of self-gratification. Impulse items appeal to the emotional side of consumers. Preventing impulsive buying involves techniques such as setting budgets before shopping and taking time to make any purchase decision. If in case of purchasing automobiles or home appliances, are considered as an emotional purchase. Automobiles in most of the cases are emotional purchase rather than rational ones.

The multiplex malls hypermarkets and online shops or markets are the modern retailing environment they have been developed as one of the major growing industry with several domestic and international players entering into the market. The major objective of this study is to understand the factors that pushes into impulsive buying.

LITURATURE REVIEW

Kacen & Lee (2002) Concluded that age is an important factor to be considered in case of impulsive behavior as they feel less risky to spend money. Impulsive buying is higher between the age of 18-39 years of age.

Priyanka & Robbie (2012) Concluded that individuals with different genders tend to have different buying behavior so women are apt to impulsive buying more than men.

Wells et al (2007) Concluded that impulsive buying behavior highly depends upon the income level of the family individual or their monthly allowance.

Block and Morwitz (1999) Concluded that impulsive buying is an item with no deliberation after the result of powerful urge.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To study all the factors that influences impulsive buying behavior in women aged between 18-25 years.
- To examine the effect of the different variables of impulsive buying.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- This study is based on the information of the representation sample group selected from a total population of a smaller lot of people hence; it does not cover the factors influencing impulsive buying behavior of the entire city or town but only a part of it.
- The analysis was conducted through questionnaire hence, there are chances that there may be any other factor(s) that influences impulsive buying other than mentioned in the questions.
- The study is only customer based. It completely ignores the marketers or sellers' efforts to attract the customers and result into impulsive buying.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This deals with description of methodology and the steps taken for collection and organization of data and presenting the findings of investigation. The methodology of research indicates the general pattern of organizing the procedures for gathering valid and reliable data or the purpose of investigation (KOTHORI,1996). The methodology of the study includes the description of research design, population, sampling technique, data collection procedures and methods of analysis.

QUESTIONNAIRE DEVELOPMENT

The data has been gathered through structured questionnaire, which has been designed on the basis on the purpose of this study.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE SIZE

The target populations were women aged between 18-25 years.

EXTENT AND SAMPLE

The study was conducted among women studying in college. For this study it was relevant to obtain a sample of about 100 respondents all them were women. All of them are between 18-25 years of age.

DATA COLLECTION

The method used for data collection was structured questionnaire. There are 13 questions. The questions are based on the age the income level or the monthly allowances, marital status. The questionnaires were thoroughly checked and edited.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

QUESTION 1: AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS:

Through the questionnaire we can conclude that most of the respondents belong to the age group of 20-25 years of age. The minimum age of the respondents is 20 years while the maximum is 25 years. Age contributes as one of the major factor for influencing the buying behavior.

QUESTION 2: MONTHLY ALLOWANCE:

The respondents had been asked about their monthly allowances. As the survey was conducted in a college, most of them are not earning. About 55% of respondents say that their allowance monthly is below Rs5000. Monthly salary or incomes or allowances directly affects the buying pattern or the impulsive buying behavior of the people.

QUESTION 3: HOW OFTEN DO YOU SHOP? (ANYTHING RANGING FROM CLOTHES TO FOOD ITEMS):

It is important to understand how often a person shops. Here majority of people have mentioned

that they shop once or twice a week.

**QUESTION 4: DO YOU BUY SOMETHING ON THE SPUR OF THE MOMENT?
(ANYTHING RANGING FROM CLOTHES TO FOOD ITEMS):**

About 75% of respondents have agreed that they do buy something on the spur of the moment. Followed by 15% who say that yes they do and 8% who do not. Buying on the spur of the moment without planning itself serves as impulsive buying.

QUESTION 5: WHAT PUSHES YOU TO BUY THINGS?

Here, most of the respondents (53%) have agreed that they buy things according to their need which is opposite of impulsive buying. The rest 20% agree to attractive prices which is one of the major causes of impulsive buying and the rest 26% say its according to any offers on the

product.

QUESTION 6: HAVE YOU EVER CONTINUED TO BUY PRODUCTS IN SPITE OF THE FINANCIAL AND FAMILY PROBLEMS YOUR PURCHASE CAUSED?

About 53% of the respondents have agreed that they sometimes have bought products or have continued buying products in spite of financial or family problems their purchase caused. This means that they are more likely to go for impulsive buying.

QUESTION 7: CAREFUL PLANNING OF PURCHASES:

About 55% of the respondents have agreed that they carefully plan their purchases while among the remaining 37 % and 6% admit they sometimes do and they never respectively.

QUESTION 8: I BUY THINGS ACCORDING TO HOW I FEEL AT THE MOMENT (ANYTHING RANGING FROM FOODS TO CLOTHES):

About 51% of the respondent have clearly mentioned that they buy things according to their mood or how they feel at that time or the moment. While 42% say they sometimes which may also mean they are into impulsive buying.

QUESTION 9: "BUY NOW THINK LATER" DESCRIBES ME:

About 48% of the respondents have agreed that “buy now think later” describes them these many people are more likely to buy things anytime of the moment while 8 % agree to it and the remaining say never.

QUESTION 10: I HAVE OFTEN BOUGHT A PRODUCT THAT I DO NOT NEED

About 8% of the people gave agreed that they often buy products that do not need while 55% think sometimes they do and the rest 35% says never.

QUESTION 11: I HAVE OFTEN BOUGHT PRODUCTS BECAUSE OF CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT OR BECAUSE MY FRIENDS HAVE IT:

About 40% of the people believe that they sometimes they buy products because of celebrity endorsements or because their friends have it. This shows that it is one of the important factors for impulsive buying while 53% say no and the remaining have agreed on it.

QUESTION 12: DO YOU SHOP TO KILL YOUR LEISURE TIME:

About 35% of people have agreed that sometimes they do shop to kill their leisure time while 57% have said no and the remaining 6% have said yes.

QUESTION 13: Are you aware of impulsive buying while shopping?

About 80% of the respondents have agreed that they are aware of impulsive buying while the rest 20% agree that they do not. Lack of awareness can also lead to impulsive buying.

FINDINGS

- In the analysis, it is seen that most of the students have the knowledge of what is impulse buying, while there are still quite a number of students who are not aware of impulse buying behavior.
- More number of the students are seen to be having 5000 or less than 5000 monthly allowance as they are not yet working and the rest are seen to be having more than 5000 monthly allowances.
- To analyze the shopping pattern, it can be seen that a larger proportion of the students shop once or twice a month, while a reasonable lot of students shopping more than twice a month followed by a few numbers of students shopping once almost every day.
- More than half of the students agree to be shopping sometimes or rarely in the spur of the moment while, a smaller number of students responded positively towards buying impulsively almost every time they shop.
- Among all the respondents, most of them responded positively towards impulse buying because of the need of the product. Whereas, a similar number of students responded equally towards impulse buying because of attractive prices and discounts and offers.
- A considerable number of students have agreed to buying impulsively sometimes even if though they have financial problems while a smaller number of students disagreed to it.
- Most of the students responded positively towards buying things according to their mood and how they feel at the time of buying without considering the prices and offers. While, others responded negatively towards buying according to their moods which can be concluded as the latter lot is more into impulsive buying than the former.
- The chart shows considerably similar lot of students agreeing to have been buying now and think later as well as others disagreeing to the fact of buying now and think later.
- Most of the responses for things bought that they do not need are positive while there are students who responded negatively towards buying things that they do not need.
- A considerable number of students responded positively towards shopping to kill their leisure time, while, a majority of the students responded against it.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study of the impulse buying behavior in young women, it can be seen that women intend to shop in the spur of the moment if they get special offers and discounts. Impulse buying is usually seen with the small things like every day essentials that are kept near the billing counter that the customers pickup impulsively while billing all of the other planned products. Here, in the study we can see that many of the students prefer buying products even if they are having financial issues, this shows that impulse buying might also lead to financial break downs among the youngsters as they tend to buy more in order to go with the trend. Creating awareness about the negative impacts of impulse buying specially among the young adults is very important in order to make them plan their expenses accordingly.

DIRECTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDIES

The research carried on could be further analyzed in the future for research purposes by other researchers and marketers through a marketer's point of view in order to understand the challenges that they often face in the marketing of a product and the ways that they follow in order to gain the attention of the customers and provide them products with reasonable pricing.

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ENCOURAGING INNOVATIVE THINKING THROUGH DIGITIZATION OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In the present competitive world Education in the right direction shape the future of the students. The demographic dividend which India has right now can be exploited through providing education in right direction. Affordability and accessibility of education in India is addressed through Reservations and Acts like Right to Education. But because of Colonial masters, India is mastered in education system where memorizing things and collecting factual information play important role. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in 2014 had ranked India 66 out of 140 countries in terms of local dynamics of innovation. This shows very dismal picture of the Indian education system. Added to this the NASSCOM – Mckinsey report “Perspective 2020: transform business, transform India” (2009) said only 26% of India’s engineering graduates were employable. This shows the lack of opportunities created by Indian education in the classrooms because of lack of infrastructure facilities namely digital modes. We have in our research paper conducted experiment explaining the concept of Inflation by employing black board and combining explanation and points, pictures and animated videos. We have taken fifty students and asked the solution to overcome the problem of Inflation, in situation without using digital tools we have succeeded in clarifying the concept but failed to build the more imagination and creativity in them for longer period. Finally we conclude that digital teaching will enhance or stimulate creativity among the students and successful in clearing the concepts.

Keywords: Education, Affordability, Development, Creativity and Innovation.

Objectives:

Objectives of the paper are as follows:

1. To see the various loopholes in Indian Education system,
2. To see how effective is digitization in Education system,
3. To find out various bottlenecks in effective utilization of digitization in Education.

Research Methodology of the Study:

This study is based on experiment conducted in the college selecting randomly fifty students as participants and secondary source of data through research papers, magazines and newspapers. By looking into experiment results and secondary data we have analyzed and concluded.

Introduction:

India is young nation in the sense that share of its youth in total population in 2011 stands at around 35%. This human potential can be efficiently utilized by way of encouraging creativity

and innovative minds in the students. Innovative ideas should be nurtured in schools and colleges, for that we should create environment in such a way that which encourages students to some creative works. Schools and colleges should have infrastructure facilities attached with committed teaching staff. In modern competitive world we have to create innovative minds for that latest available technologies should be adopted like digital technology. Primarily Digital Education has 3 components: content, technology platforms, delivery infrastructure ^[1]. Therefore we need to focus on the content, platform and infrastructure then only effective education can be delivered through the digital mode.

In this research paper to find out the impact of teaching backed by digital tools on their skills we have conducted an experiment taking fifty students. First we taught the economic concept Inflation through chalk and talk way to randomly selected fifty students and then the same fifty members were taught through smart board using digital tools that is projector using animated teaching on inflation. We have asked the question that how to overcome the problem of Inflation before and after digital teaching. The students have answered more comprehensively during the teaching backed by digital tools. This is because they have imagined clearly with the help of animated one and answered well. With the overall analysis we have come to the conclusion that digital way of teaching has more positive impact and encourages creativity by way of clarifying the concepts well through pictures and animations.

Negative sides of our Education System:

Indian traditional education system was focused more on practicality like Guru Kula type of education system. That was followed by the British education system which focused more on British interest than intellectual improvement among the Indians. This education system made students only for remembering the information only. There are number of negative aspect in our education system that totally kills creativity and interest among the children.

The diagram clearly shows that present education system focuses mainly on the memorizing the things that will ultimately leads to creative thinking, interest and encouragement from students

Diagram Showing Present Education System

taking back seat. This education system does not provide security to our students as far as employability is considered. This was supported by some study on higher education last year estimated that fewer than 15% of graduates with Master's Degree were employable.

Therefore we should create a education system that encourages creative skill, encourage innovation etc. The INFO-TAINMENT

combination involved in digital education makes it more practical, applicable and relatable to our life and surroundings in an interesting manner ^[2]. The need of the hour is to encourage digital education for our students to compete with the competitive global world.

Results and Discussion:

Digital Education can be defined as the use of a combination of technology, digital content and instruction in the education system to make it more effective and efficient than the traditional education system [3]. The adopted digital technology should be tuned in such a way that should ensure the local needs. To know the impact of the digital education on the students we have conducted the experiment in our college by randomly selecting students.

In our college C.G.Bellad GFGC Akkialur, Hangal (Tq), Haveri (Dt), Karnataka, have conducted an experiment related to the impact of the Digital education on creativity and understanding of the concepts. For this we have taken economic concept called Inflation, and randomly selected fifty students. Initially we have taught the inflation with chalk and talk method, explained the concept clearly. This method clearly explained the concept, but here unable to touch their imagination that much; this was assessed by the questions posed on them.

The concept selected was Inflation, in chalk and talk the concept explained clearly but same content explained with the digital tools viz. smart board, projector etc. in the traditional method explanation backed with examples but in the digital teaching we have included pictures, animations etc. After teaching we posed a question that how to overcome the problem of inflation? The Answer by the same students was recorded. The answer to the question contains both supply side and demand side answers, but more concept clarity was needed to answer to imagine the supply side answers. We have listed their response in percent form.

Table 1: Showing Answer by the students in each mode of teaching

Mode of Teaching	Answers	
	Demand Side Answers	Supply side Answers
Chalk and Talk	99%	1%
Digital Teaching	45%	55%

When we analyze the responses collected we could easily find out that education through digital tools yielded better results compared to the chalk and talk method. In the traditional method of teaching we make students to imagine but in the digital teaching through the pictures and animations their imaginations are directed in the desired direction and creative thinking can be influenced.

We have also listed the level of interaction by the students before and after concept clarity through digital mode. That is the quality of answers given by the students when questions about Inflation posed in various angles. The overall effect of the digital education is charted out in the bar diagram in the below.

When we clearly analyzed level of quality answers after and before Digital teaching we could see that the level of quality answers increased much in the digital teaching. We have divided the quality of answers into three categories i.e. below level, average level and higher level based on the closeness of the answers to the reality. We have recorded the quality answers given by the students and put in the bar diagram which clearly indicates that the level of interaction and

quality answers were improved. This shows the positive impact of the Digital education on the students by stimulating the interest and creative skills among the students.

Findings from the experiments:

The key in developing the effectiveness of digital learning on teaching lies in teachers ^[4]. The success of the any mode of education system depends on the teachers, take for instance even digital education also needs human face to tune ethics and morality in to the education system. We have come across with some interesting findings while doing this experiment with digital mode; they are as follows

- ✓ Digital teaching with the help of figures, pictures and animation will stimulate interest among the students,
- ✓ The digital education will encourage creative thinking among the students by way of shaping the imagination in the right direction,
- ✓ It involves active participation by the students because of understanding made easy,
- ✓ Difficult concept can easily be explained through the digital mode of teaching,
- ✓ Repetition can also be made easy, quick assessment can be done through this processes,
- ✓ Understanding abilities of the students can be easily identified through the digital education process,
- ✓ This process makes students to remember the concepts longer time, because of the usage of pictures and animations etc.
- ✓ Easy updating can be made through the digital education because it is easy to update the current information in PPT's and newly developed animations can be easily included.

Challenges we face to go digital education:

We have listed above the various positive side of the digital education, but there are many negative side of digital education for its implementation. They are as follows:

- ✓ Teachers' should have minim technical mind in handling the digital education tools,
- ✓ There should be a balance between talk and animation,
- ✓ Rigorous training should be given to the teaching community,
- ✓ We should update ourselves regularly,
- ✓ Government's initiatives needed for the effective digital education in the country,
- ✓ Operating cost is high that is acting as the obstacle for the implementation of digital education in the country,
- ✓ Maintaining the balance between students, teachers and technology should be there, the right mix of them will yield better results,
- ✓ Educational institutions in the village level will face some kind of obstacle because of their availability of digital education delivery facilities.

These are the some of the important problems of that comes in the way of implementing the digital education.

Conclusion:

The present competitive world provide platform to those who have creative thinking and innovative minds. The necessary facilities should be provided to the young India to exhibit their talent, one among them is to provide education through the digital mode. The education should reach everybody that can easily achieve through the digital education. The right to Education is rightly achieved through digital education because the digital education not only ensures equity but also affordability. Right content and method of delivery in the digital education will ensure creative thinking, innovative mind and interest among the students.

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ROLE OF AGE IN INVESTMENT DECISIONS

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ABSTRACT

Individuals project various biases in their investment decisions. It may vary from emotional to cognitive biases. Amongst many demographic factors age is analyzed in the present study. The objective is to observe influence of age on behavioral biases which later will affect investment decision. Investors across various cities of India were selected as sample respondents. Data was collected using structured questionnaire. The study applied chi-square and kruskal wallis test to analyze the influence of age on decisions like expected return, portfolio size, investment objective, investment avenues etc. The study concluded that investors across various age groups vary in their investment decisions. Decisions are affected by cognitive ability of an individual and risk tolerance level. Also responsibilities, capital base and income levels vary across various age categories. All these forces play a crucial role in financial decision making.

Key words: Age, behavioral biase, investment decision, chi square, demographics

1 INTRODUCTION

Individuals often have to take certain decisions. These decisions may be big or small. Some decisions are easy and straight forward while others are complicated and require detailed analysis and multi-step approach to make a decision. An area of study known as “cognitive psychology” can be referred to understand how people make a choice. What factors influences their decisions and several heuristics in the process of decision making.

Decisions are integral part of everyone’s life. The process of making a decision is a complex mechanism of human thinking. It involves a structural procedure and gets affected by various factors and course of action. Some individual differences may also affect the decision. Age is one of such difference that is being long studied in various disciplines. Evidence suggests that age declines an individual’s cognitive abilities. Working memory, speed of processing and executive functioning begins to decline in mid-20s and advances into 70s. The three strategies used by individuals while taking a decision as identified by researchers are cognitive, heuristics and biases. The use of these strategies also gets affected by decision maker’s age. Old adults are more likely to use heuristics and biases than young adults. Age related changes in decision making seems to get affected by the environment in which decision is made, personal relevance of a decision and experience with the decision domain.

Traditional theory of finance states that investor’s make decisions rationally and always follow sound logics while taking a decision. But behavioral scientist proclaims that decisions are made using thumb rules and shortcuts. There is no rational thinking guiding an individual’s decision

making process. Investor's gets swayed by their moods, emotions and past experiences. Hence their choices are an outcome of irrational investment decisions. With respect to age it is believed that increasing age leads to a shift in individual's basis of decision making from optimization to satisfaction. Growing by age people tend to rely on their experiences and prefer making a familiar choice rather than exploring new opportunities. There are many such aspects related to age and decision making. Therefore the present study aims to bring out neurobiological and behavioral changes associated with age of an individual in context to investment decision making.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Yoo (1994) identified a non linear relationship between portfolio allocation and aging of an individual. A cross sectional study was conducted using time series analysis. The findings of the study suggests that young as well as retired individuals prefers less risky investment options as compared to middle aged individuals. Individuals from different age group have different priorities when they determine their portfolio composition.

Korniotis and Kumar (2011) studied investment decisions of older individual investors. Outcome of the study suggests that "older and more experienced investors hold less risky portfolios, exhibit stronger preference for diversification, trade less frequently, exhibits a greater propensity for year-end tax loss selling, and exhibit weaker behavioral biases. Thus, their choices reflect greater knowledge about investing." Older investors are worst in applying investment knowledge and possess worst investment skills. The adverse effect of aging dominates positive effect of experience in case of investment decisions.

Mont (2011) focused on analyzing investment decisions made by young and old investors. The outcome of the research suggest that older investors display a variability in nucleus accumbens activity because of which they tend to make irrational and bold decisions. Older investors showed similar willingness as young investors to invest in stock. But their approach to decision making was distracted and rash. Because of which they many times ended up making a bad decision. Young investors seem to take more cautious decisions as they have to pay off debt and plan future.

Charles and Kasilingam (2013) analyzed how investor's age determines his investment behavior. They analyzed various demographic biases. Impact of these demographic variables was studied with respect to behavioral biases that later on effect the financial decisions. To analyze they considered 742 individual investors that invest or trade on Indian stock market. Cross tabulation and correspondence analysis was used to analyze the collected data. Statistical software SPSS was used to apply statistical tools. The study concluded that age is the most influential factor amongst all other factors that has a bearing on investment decisions of individual investors.

Onsomu (2015) studied the effect of age on investor decisions at the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Kenya. There were four age brackets considered for the study 18-30, 31-40, 41-50 and above 50 years. The outcome of the study suggests that there exists a significant relationship between age and overconfidence bias. Investors within age group 18-30 years were most affected while investors in 31-40 age group was least impacted. Representative, confirmation and disposition bias was displayed by investors across all age brackets.

Gamble et.al (2015) used panel data of elderly individuals with an average age of 82 years. The objective of the study is to analyze the effect of declining cognition on financial decision making. The study concluded that declining cognition is associated with significant decline in financial literacy. Elderly were found to take help for their finances mainly from their spouse. Despite of declining cognition elderly were found to have confidence in their financial knowledge and management of finances.

Khoo (2016) claims that people in same age group tend to share certain circumstances in life owing to which some correlation was found between age of investors and their investment strategies. Young people have more risk taking capacity as they have more time to recover their losses if any. The earning power of older people is generally more as compared to young people and hence their starting capital is also high. Commitment and number of dependents tend to grow as one get older, hence older will take less risky decisions. But in reality their exist exceptions to these rules. If an individual belongs to a wealthy family or has made fortune at young age then his investment strategy may be different. Lastly it also depends on individuals preferences.

Shashikant (2019) identified that people find information load tiring as they age. One's ability to associate specific information with specific people, product or processes deteriorates with age. Therefore it is difficult for older people to filter information, handle complex product feature and shift their objective. Elders were found to go by generic names and specific brands. Their decisions are based on familiarity and past experience. The article further highlights various ways in which help can be extended to elderly in their decision making process.

Cannivet (2019) tried to identify what is the prime age group of an investor. Outcomes of many researches were discussed in his article. After analyzing it was concluded that older investors also follow the rules of investment but the effectiveness declines as one ages because of decrease in cognitive ability. Mostly people have an investing blind spot after the age of 60 which leads to poor financial decisions.

According to Edelman Financial Engine the previous researches that claims that older people cannot process much information due to decline in their cognitive ability is not necessarily true. The article cite outcome of a new study conducted at University of California and states that the financial expertise as well as knowledge that you gain in your lifetime offsets that natural decline in your cognitive ability. They also conclude that crystallized brain that is developed through knowledge & experience is more important in finance decision making than fluid brain which relates to logical thinking & information processing.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

3.1 Objective of the study

- 1) To segment individual investors on the basis of their demographic attributes.
- 2) To analyze the impact of age on investor's investment decisions.

3.2 Hypotheses

- 1) H1.1 There is no significant difference in size of investment portfolio of investors belonging to different age groups.

- 2) H1.2 There is no significant difference in return expectation between investors belonging to different age groups.
- 3) H1.3 There is no significant difference in investment objective of investors belonging to different age groups.
- 4) H1.4 There is no significant difference in frequency of portfolio revision of investors belonging to different age groups.
- 5) H1.5 There is no significant difference in risk preference of investors belonging to different age groups.
- 6) H1.6 There is no significant difference between investors belonging to different age groups in their preference of investment avenues.

3.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

The purpose of the research is both exploratory and descriptive. The study identifies demographic profile of investors. It is exploratory as it compares various groups of individuals divided on the basis of their age. It is also descriptive as it attempts to identify investment decision making process of investors.

3.4 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The universe for the present study comprises of all individual investors, while the target population will include all individual investors in India. Sampling unit can be defined as individuals who invest their savings in financial market. Individuals can be male or female, employed across any occupation category, and might have attended any level of education. With regards to age the sampling unit defines an age limit of above 18 years.

3.5 SAMPLE DESIGN

As the population was too large and heterogeneous Non – Probabilistic Sampling technique was used. The methods used to identify appropriate samples were Judgmental and Convenience sampling methods.

3.6 SAMPLE SIZE

The total number of questionnaires distributed was 1000. 558 questionnaires were received. From 558 questionnaires received, 545 fully responded questionnaires were identified. Thus the response rate was 55.8%.

3.7 TOOL FOR DATA COLLECTION

Data was collected using a self administered questionnaire. The first section of the questionnaire recorded variables like age, gender, education, occupation, yearly income.

The second section of questionnaire included questions related to financial decision of an individual. Most of the variables are measured using a close-ended multiple choice format

3.8 DATA ANALYSIS

Collected data is analyzed using statistical tools and are presented using tables and graphs. The analysis is carried out using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.0 for

Windows. The data analysis methods used were descriptive statistics, cross tabulation, bar charts, Chi-Square test, Kruskal Wallis test and Mann Whitney test.

4. Data Analysis and Results

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Demographic detail of respondents was summarized to analyze the basic features of sample chosen for study. The descriptive statistics comprises of list of variables considered and sample distribution across all the variables. As can be seen from table 1 that the sample includes 326 males and 219 females. Majority of respondents belong to 26-35 and 36-45 age groups. Percentage distribution of sample as per their educational qualification was found to be 4.8% with H.Sc as their education background, 25.7% are graduate, 41.8% are post graduate and 27.7% are professionals. Hence it can be said that majority respondents have above graduation level of education. Similarly distribution based on occupation shows that 48.6% belong to service class followed by business class (23.7%) and professionals (21.3%). Income distribution shows that 24.6% respondents have annual income less than 5 lakhs, 32.7% belongs to 5 lakhs to 10 lakhs income group, 26.4% belongs to 10 lakhs to 15 lakhs income group and 16.3% belong to income group above 15 lakhs.

Table 1: Demographic and Geographic Characteristics of the Sample

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	326	59.8	59.8
	Female	219	40.2	100.0
	Total	545	100.0	100.0
Age (in years)	18-25	79	14.5	14.5
	26-35	244	44.8	59.3
	36-45	159	29.2	88.4
	Above 45	63	11.6	100.0
	Total	545	100.0	100.0
Education	H.SC	26	4.8	4.8
	Graduate	140	25.7	30.5
	Post Graduate	228	41.8	72.3
	Professional	151	27.7	100.0
	Total	545	100.0	100.0
Occupation	Service	265	48.6	48.6
	Business	129	23.7	72.3
	Housewife	35	6.4	78.7
	Professional	116	21.3	100
	Total	545	100	100
Yearly Income	Less than 5 lakhs	134	24.6	24.6
	5 lakhs to 10 lakhs	178	32.7	57.2
	10 lakhs to 15 lakhs	144	26.4	83.7
	Above 15 lakhs	89	16.3	100
	Total	100	100	100

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

The hypotheses of the study were analyzed using various statistical tools like chi square test, and Kruskal Wallis test. These tests were applied to various hypotheses depending upon the measurement scale of the variables.

H_{1.1} There is no significant difference in size of investment portfolio between investors of different age group.

Table 2: Investment Portfolio * Age Group Cross Tabulation

Investment Portfolio	18-25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	Total
0 – Rs 50000	28	54	22	11	115
Rs 50000 – Rs 100000	17	43	14	7	81
Rs 100000 – Rs 500000	20	77	57	24	178
Rs 500000 – Rs 1000000	9	51	41	10	111
Above Rs 1000000	5	19	25	11	60
Total	79	244	159	63	545

Table 3: Chi-Square Test Investment Portfolio * Age

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square (a)	44.029	12	0.000*
Likelihood Ratio	44.48	12	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	26.62	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	545		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.94.

*Differences are significant at 1%

Outcome of cross tabulation between investment portfolio size and age of investors reveals that investors with portfolio size between 18 to 25 years of age have low investments while investors in 26 to 45 years age brackets display high amount of investment. Above 45 years of age portfolio size is generally in middle range.

Chi Square test was applied to identify relationship between age and portfolio size of investors.

The outcome of the study suggests that null hypothesis was rejected at 1% level of significance (Table 3). Thus it can be said that there exists a difference between portfolio size of investors across different age brackets.

H_{1.2} There is no significant difference in return expectation between investors of different age group.

Table 4: Expected Return * Age Group Cross Tabulation

Expected Return	18-25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	Total
Up to 10%	39	85	46	22	192
11% to 15%	19	89	59	20	187
16% to 20%	15	48	42	13	118
Above 20%	6	22	12	8	48
Total	79	244	159	63	545

Table 5: Chi-Square Test Expected Return * Age Group

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square (a)	13.436	9	0.044*
Likelihood Ratio	13.129	9	0.157
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.741	1	0.053
N of Valid Cases	545		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.55.

*Differences are significant at 5%

It can be observed from the cross tabulation table that investors belonging to below 35 years and above 45 years of age category display high expected returns. While investors in age bracket 36 to 45 years have comparatively high expectation.

Influence of age over return expectation was tested using chi-square test. The result of the test revealed the statistics value as .044 which is less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected in this case. This indicates existence of an association between these two variables.

H_{1.3} There is no significant difference in investment objective of investors of different age group.

Table 6: Mean Rank Investment Objective * Age

Investment Objective	Age (in years)	N	Mean Rank
Capital Appreciation	18-25	79	298.72
	26-35	244	253.77
	36-45	159	279.92
	Above 45	63	297.76
	Total	545	
Regular Income	18-25	79	276.46
	26-35	244	276.88
	36-45	159	277.38
	Above 45	63	242.56
	Total	545	
Future Security	18-25	79	254.51
	26-35	244	273.45
	36-45	159	267.14
	Above 45	63	309.24

	Total	545	
Tax Benefit	18-25	79	260.75
	26-35	244	288.44
	36-45	159	265.92
	Above 45	63	246.43
	Total	545	
Status Quo	18-25	79	265.33
	26-35	244	273.83
	36-45	159	274.38
	Above 45	63	275.91
	Total	545	

Lower the mean, higher the preference

Table 7: Kruskal Wallis Test Investment Objective * Age

Investment Objectives	Capital Appreciation	Regular Income	Future Security	Tax Benefit	Status Quo
Chi-Square	8.03	2.78	4.852	5.19	0.249
Df	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	0.045*	0.427*	0.183*	0.158*	0.969*

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Age (in years)

*Differences are significant at 5%

Preference of investment objective of investors across different age category is observed using mean ranks as shown in table 6. Investors in age group 18 to 25 years give more preference to future security while investors in age bracket of 26 to 35 years gives priority to capital growth. 36 to 45 years of age group investors prefer tax benefit while above 45 years prefer regular income.

Investment objective as a dependent variable was tested against independent variable age by applying Kruskal Wallis test. The outcome of the test reveals only in case of capital growth null hypothesis was rejected. For all other objectives null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance.

H_{1.4} There is no significant difference in frequency of portfolio revision of investors of different age group.

Table 8: Portfolio Revision * Age Cross Tabulation

Portfolio Revision	Age (in years)				Total
	18-25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	
Monthly	34	85	19	6	144
Quarterly	17	59	27	6	109
Half Yearly	11	48	27	8	94
Yearly	10	37	49	38	134
More than a year	7	15	37	5	64
Total	79	244	159	63	545

Table 9: Chi Square test Portfolio Revision * Age

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square (a)	8.741a	12	0.025*
Likelihood Ratio	8.833	12	0.717
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.459	1	0.498
N of Valid Cases	545		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.40.

*Differences are significant at 5%

Frequency of portfolio revision was cross tabulated across different age groups. It was observed that Young investors in the age bracket of 18-25 years and 26-35 years usually revised their portfolios more frequently than investors above 35 years. Young investors mostly revised every month and investors above 35 years mostly revised every year (Table 8).

Impact of age on frequency of portfolio revision was identified using chi square analysis. The P value of .025 shows that null hypothesis was rejected at 5% level of significance indicating no impact of age of investor on frequency of portfolio revision (Table 9).

H_{1.5} There is no significant difference in risk preference of investors of different age group.

Table 10: Risk Preference * Age Group Cross Tabulation

Risk Preference	18-25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	Total
No risk at all	6	8	5	5	24
Below average risk	22	19	48	37	126
Average risk	25	87	84	11	207
Above average risk	18	105	13	5	141
Very high risk	8	25	9	5	47
Total	79	244	159	63	545

Table 11: Chi-Square Test Risk Preference * Age Group

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square (a)	11.723	12	0.046*
Likelihood Ratio	11.387	12	0.496
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.01	1	0.919
N of Valid Cases	545		

*Differences are significant at 5%

Risk appetite of investors was understood by asking them to choose the risk preference they generally keep in mind before choosing a financial instrument. On classifying risk preference along with age of investors it was found that investors in age bracket of 18-25 years and 36-45 years were found to either prefer average risk or below average risk. Risk appetite of investors in age group 26-35 years was high in comparison to other age groups. They preferred above average risk or average risk. Investors above 45 years of age were reported to opt for low risk investment options

Chi square test statistics was used to assess the influence of age on risk appetite of investors. A calculated statistics value 0.046 reveals that the null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance and also verify the existence of an association between risk preference of investors and their age.

H_{1.6} There is no significant difference among investors of different age group in their preference of investment avenues

Table 12: Mean Ranks Investment Avenues * Age

	Age (in years)	N	Mean Rank
Bank Fixed Deposit and Other Government Securities	18-25	79	247.63
	26-35	244	275.6
	36-45	159	276.38
	Above 45	63	266.67
	Total	545	
Bonds and Debentures	18-25	79	264.94
	26-35	244	273.83
	36-45	159	276.36
	Above 45	63	271.4
	Total	545	
Equity	18-25	79	276.83
	26-35	244	273.2
	36-45	159	271.14
	Above 45	63	272.14
	Total	545	
Mutual Funds	18-25	79	280.68
	26-35	244	260.83
	36-45	159	258.42
	Above 45	63	276.48
	Total	545	
Derivatives	18-25	79	288.1
	26-35	244	281.65
	36-45	159	282.8
	Above 45	63	286.23
	Total	545	

Lower the mean, higher the preference

Table 13: Kruskal Wallis Test Investment Avenue * Age

	Bank Fixed Deposit and Other Government Securities	Bonds and Debentures	Equity	Mutual Funds	Derivatives
Chi-Square	2.781	0.306	0.077	2.515	3.369
Df	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	0.027*	0.959*	0.994*	0.473*	0.338*

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Age (in years)

**Differences are significant at 5%*

Investor's preference was recorded by taking ranks for five investment avenues. The mean of ranks was then calculated and classified across different age category. It can be seen from the rank allotted that young investors belonging to age group 18-25 years and above 45 years preferred bank fixed deposit and other government securities as they might be willing to take less risk. Investors in other two age groups of 26-35 years and 36-45 years preferred mutual funds

In order to examine influence of age on investment avenue choice of investor kruskal Wallis test was applied. The outcome of the test shows that null hypothesis is accepted in all cases except for bank fixed deposits and other government securities. Null hypothesis was rejected at 5% level of significance in case of bank fixed deposits and other government securities. This signifies that no difference in choice of investment avenues with respect to age was found for other avenues.

5. CONCLUSION

Age dependent behavior in your financial decision has many useful implications and therefore it has been long studied by many researchers. The outcome of the present study is in line with the previous researches that states that age influence overall financial decision of an individual. Although now a days there is no age bar as far as information availability is concerned but still the ability to process this information vary across age groups.

From the analysis of findings of the study it can be suggested that in the early years of investing that is in 20s and 30s one should focus aggressively on growth, should take active part in investment decisions and aim to take maximum benefit of compounding. At the age of starting 40s one reaches peak earning time, therefore it's the best time to balance your investments between growth and steadier investment options. Your investment choice in 50s must match with your retirement goals, income levels, tax liability and projected retirement income. Your age determines and influence many important areas of day to day and long term decision making. Therefore it must be consciously considered when taking investment decisions.

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THE STUDY OF PHYSICAL FITNESS PARAMETERS ON FEMALE VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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ABSTRACT

The intention of this study is to reveal the effect of physical fitness parameters on female volleyball players in the age group of 16 to 18 years. In this study, a total of 12 female players from SDM sports hostel, Ujire, Mangalore participated. Anthropometric and physical fitness measurements were recorded and analyzed. To be specific, age, height and weight were taken for anthropometric profile and for physical fitness profile, explosive strength measurements were taken. In addition to that, endurance and agility tests were also documented. A 12 minute endurance run and 4x10 m shuttle run test for both endurance and agility tests were conducted respectively. The recorded data was interpreted to determine the physical fitness of the players.

Keywords: Physical fitness, volleyball.

INTRODUCTION

One of the important factors of a professional volleyball player is the physical fitness. Different tests are conducted to conclude the physical fitness of the player. Endurance run, agility run, jump and reach height test, balance and flexibility are few of the tests [1]. The extreme volleyball activities include repeated jumping and throwing activities [2]. To perform all these activities, one should have a good anthropometric profile [3, 4 and 5]. Having all desired anthropometric measurements is not enough to call a player as a physical fit volleyball player. One should also pass through the tests of muscular strength, explosive strength, speed, flexibility and balance [6]. The objective of the present study is to analyse different physical fitness capabilities, explosive strength and finally, the impact of all the anthropometric and physical fitness parameters on the female volleyball players.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS AND DISCUSSION

The female student players of SDM sports hostel, Ujire from Mangalore (under 18 category-female) were taken into consideration for our study. To know the explosive strength of

volleyball players, each one of the players were investigated with standing reach height and Jump-reach height (both measured in metres) in addition to their age (years), height (in centimetre) and weight (in kilogram).

Table I: The Anthropometric and Physical fitness measurements of female volleyball players.

Players No.	Age (yrs)	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	Explosive Strength		Endurance -12 min run (in meters)	Agility – shuttle run 4x10m (in seconds : microseconds)
				Standing Reach (in m)	Jump and Reach (in m)		
1	18	154	43	2.03	2.31	1650	12:85
2	17	166	56	2.18	2.45	3860	12:41
3	17	169	52	2.25	2.51	3930	12:52
4	16	169	58	2.24	2.56	4150	11:88
5	17	165	50	2.18	2.44	2040	12:68
6	18	169	51	2.24	2.50	2000	12:31
7	16	152	44	1.96	2.19	1650	12:96
8	18	170	51	2.22	2.48	1650	13:42
9	16	155	42	2.04	2.28	1920	13:47
10	18	171	57	2.33	2.64	4240	11:86
11	16	161	46	2.12	2.34	2650	12:43
12	17	167	55	2.23	2.46	2040	12:76

After getting the basic anthropometric measurements and explosive strength height measurements, endurance and agility tests were conducted. In endurance test, a 12 minute run was conducted. In agility test, a shuttle run of 4x10 m run was conducted. All the above anthropometric and physical fitness measurements were taken as per the rules and regulations. Table I shows the anthropometric and physical fitness measurements of 12 female volleyball players.

From the data collected, one crucial interpretation can be made. Players with the highest anthropometric profile measurements are showing good explosive strength, phenomenal endurance and agility capabilities. With the highest explosive strengths (0.32 m and 0.31 m), achieving longest distances in 12 minute endurance run (4150 m and 4240 m) and a impressive agile profile achieved in 4x10 m shuttle run (11:88 and 11:86 in s:µs), it is quite easy to say the player no. 4 and 10 are the ones to have a perfect physical fitness profile. From the table 1, highlighted readings of two players, player no. 4 and player no. 10, are having a healthy anthropometric profile and also a desirable physical fitness.

CONCLUSION

Physical fitness of a player influences the sports career span. In order to have a good physical fitness profile, a player has to begin the preparation work with building a good anthropometric

profile and maintaining it. When all the parameter values of fitness and anthropometric measurements come in the optimal range, then a player can feel safe to undergo volleyball training activities. Even minor injuries can be minimised and avoided if the player is having a healthy physical fitness profile.

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STUDENTS' PERCEPTION TOWARDS CORE BANKING INCONVENIENCE& REMEDIES: A CASE STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO RURAL STUDENTS OF MANGALORE TALUK OF DAKSHINA KANNADA

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ABSTRACT:

Technological advancements in the country gave great push to the banking field and brought massive changes in the mode of banking operations. Installation of Core Banking Solutions paved the way for the introduction of various digital initiatives by the bankers, which are highly appreciated by younger generation customers, particularly by students. This paper attempts to highlight the digital inconvenience in rural parts of Managalore taluk of Dakshina Kannada district, caused due to infrastructure deficit like lack of digital identity, lack of high speed network coverage, safe cyber etc. The study is based upon the opinions given by 100 rural undergraduate students of Managalore taluk of Dakshina Kannada district, residing in Haleyangadi, Pavanje, Challairu, Thokur and Aikala region. Majority of students, particularly female students are relatively recent entrants to internet based services. The study is carried out by conducting a survey by using a structured questionnaire. Understanding the attitude of students towards digital initiatives of Core Banking Solutions, their expectations from digital initiatives, and understanding the digital inconvenience faced by the students are the objectives of study,

Key words: Technology advancements, Core Banking Solutions, Digital initiatives, Digital inconvenience

INTRODUCTION:

One of the latest technological developments in the field of banking in recent times is the concept of digitalization. Paperless transactions through computers and mobile phones are most common among younger generation customers. In fact digitalization of transactions is made possible because of the compulsory installation of Core Banking Solutions by Bankers as per the directives issued by Reserve Bank of India. Digital India campaign launched by our honorable Prime minister Sri Narendra Modi on 1st July 2015 is a great step considering the need for economic development and prosperity of the country. But there are also a lot of problems and difficulties being faced by everyone at some or other points, needless to say, including in Digital

banking field. Lack of knowledge about the latest development in the field of technology, fear about the security of transactions and poor internet connectivity are the major drawbacks for digitalization of banking transactions in some of the rural areas of the country, including in Dakshina Kannada district.

OBJECTIVES:

- a) To know the perceptions of rural students of Managalore taluk towards digital banking
- b) To understand the expectations of the respondents towards digital banking
- c) To focus on inconveniences faced by rural students of Managalore taluk in using various digital initiatives of Core Banking Solutions

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY:

Digital inconvenience is the major issue tickling the minds of bankers in the process of implementation of digital banking strategies including CBS. Installation of Core Banking Software involves huge investment, and it requires 100% information technology support. India, being a country with mass rural population, striving very hard to make this digital India campaign very popular in every field including the banking field. Moreover, this topic is of utmost relevance considering efforts put up by bankers to improvise and satisfy the requirements of varied types of customers. Hence this study is undertaken to understand the problems faced by rural students of Managalore taluk in using various digital initiatives of Core Banking Solutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Chirag Patel, Darshan Ranpura etl.(2013) in their research article “Rural Banking Through Internet: A Study on Use of Internet Banking Among Rural Consumers” opined that role of rural banks in Indian financial sector is important, but not pre eminent. Rural banking is more inclusive of low income group families whose usage level of technological devices like smart phones and computers is lower. In the recent past, since one year they have been using internet banking mainly for balance enquiry and their usage of internet banking for other purposes is very limited.

Sahadeb Sukla Dasa(2016) in his research paper “ Study of digital banking facilities: with reference to Guwahati in Kamrup (metro) district of Assam” threw light on various digital banking services provided by banks to customers in Assam. He found from his study that Network failure, Error in operation, No security for internet dealing, No Authenticated records, Low Speed and Delay are the main problems faced by the bankers in digital banking.

Ameena Farooqui and P.Rajani (2017) in their research article “E-Banking Issues & Challenges” analysed the progress of internet banking in India. They have highlighted Security risk, lack of trust factor in internet banking, Lack of customer awareness, Fear of disclosing private information, failure to adopt global technology as the main challenges restricting the adoption of internet banking in India.

Raghavendra Nayak (2018) in his research article “A Conceptual study on digitalization of banking-issues and challenges” opined that digitalisation of banking transactions is concerned with providing efficient services to customers along with a large opportunity to gain in the years to come. Higher capital formation in the banking sector is the outcome of digitalisation of banking. But digital move in rural parts of the country is not that encouraging as, many problems and challenges have to be addressed in rural parts of the economy while introducing concept of digital banking. According to him, providing digital infrastructure to rural parts of the country, creating awareness among rural customers about digital initiatives are major challenges on the part of bankers.

Several researchers have studied the advantages and challenges of Digital banking which is the outcome of Core Banking Solutions installed by the bankers. But hitherto no study is made about Students’ perception towards Core Banking inconvenience& remedies in Mangalore Taluk. Hence to fill this research gap, this study is undertaken.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study is empirical and analytical in nature. Both Primary and Secondary data are used for the purpose of study. Primary data is collected by conducting a survey among 100 students of rural parts of Mangalore Taluk residing in Haleyangadi, Pavanje, Challairu, Thokur and Aikala region. Secondary data is incorporated from Journals, newspapers and internet. Descriptive statistics Mean, Standard Deviation and Percentage Mean are the Statistical tools used for the Analysis and interpretation of data.

HYPOTHESES:

I. Core Banking Channels and willingness of rural students to use them for their banking operations

H0: Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are not willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations

H1: Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations

II. Perceptions of respondents about Core banking inconveniences in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

H0: Respondents perceive that, there are no inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk.

H1: Respondents perceive that, there ar inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

DATA ANALYSIS:

Table 1: Demographic profile of Respondents

Demographic factors	Classification	Number of Respondents	Percent
Gender	Male	45	45
	Female	55	55
Age group	18-20 years	35	35
	20-22 years	38	38
	22 to 24 years	23	23
	24 to 26 years	04	04
Monthly Family income	Less than Rs.20,000	15	15
	Rs. 20,000 to Rs.30,000	20	30
	Rs.30,000 to Rs.40,000	33	33
	Rs.40,000 to Rs.50,000	22	22
	Rs.50,000 and above	10	10
Educational course Opted for study	PUC	04	04
	Graduation	47	47
	Post Graduation	15	15
	Professional Course	24	24
	Diploma course	10	10

Source: Primary data

From Table 1, it is clear that both male and female students of different age group belonging to different family income groups, pursuing different educational courses are surveyed for collecting their opinions regarding Core Banking Solutions and their inconvenience& remedies.

Table 2: Distribution of students on the basis of their perception regarding Core Banking Solutions

Core Banking Channels help in different ways and Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are willing to use Core	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean/SD	%Mean
	00 (0%)	02 (2%)	00 (0%)	54 (54%)	44 (44%)	3.42±0.5379	81.5%

banking channels for their banking operations							
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Source: primary data

Testing of Hypothesis:

III. Core Banking Channels and willingness of rural students to use them for their banking operations

H0: Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are not willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations

H1: Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations

Table 2 clearly shows that none of the respondents (zero percent) strongly disagree, 2 percent of respondents disagree, zero percent of respondents neither agree nor disagree, while 54 percent of the respondents agree and 44 percent of respondents strongly agree that Core banking channels have been useful in different ways and rural students of Mangalore Taluk are willing to use them for their banking operations.

The percentage mean shows that 81.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 3.42 ± 0.5379) respondents strongly opine that Core banking channels have been useful in different ways and rural students of Mangalore Taluk are willing to use them for their banking operations as it falls in the category of 81% to 100%.

Hence null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is justified. We therefore conclude that Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations.

Table 3: Perceptions of respondents about CORE BANKING Inconveniences

Sl No	Problems	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean/SD	% Mean
1	Digital illiteracy is the problem for the success of Core Banking system in rural areas of Mangalore taluk	00 (0%)	38 (38%)	00 (00%)	50 (50%)	12 (12%)	2.74±0.664	68.5%
2	Inadequate Digital net	00 (0%)	00 (0%)	28 (28%)	38 (38%)	34 (34%)	4.0600	81.2

	work is a problem for Core banking in rural areas)		±.79308	%
3	Rural customers have greater fear about safety and security of transactions and about internet fraud	00 (0%)	00 (0%)	00 (0%)	50 (50%)	50 (50%)	3.5±0.505	87.5%
4	Digital connectivity is not good in rural areas	08 (8%)	32 (32%)	00 (0%)	42 (42%)	18 (18%)	2.70±0.864	67.5%
5	Network failure, low speed and delay in conducting the transactions are the major problems in rural areas	00 (0%)	24 (24%)	00 (00%)	46 (46%)	30 (30%)	3.06±0.739	76.5%

Source: primary data

Testing of Hypothesis:

IV. Perceptions of respondents about Core banking inconveniences in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

H0: Respondents perceive that, there are no inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

H1: Respondents perceive that, there are inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

Table 3 shows Mean, Standard deviation and Percentage mean calculated on the perceptions of respondents about the inconvenience in the usage of Core banking channels .Percentage mean on each factor falls in the category of 61% to 100% which clearly shows that respondents agree that

there are inconveniences in the usage of CBS in rural areas. Mean and Standard deviation presented in table 3 on various factors also justify the same.

Hence null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is justified. We therefore conclude that there are inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk.

FINDINGS:

- 54 percent of the respondents agree and 44 percent of respondents strongly agree that Core banking channels have been useful in different ways and rural students of Mangalore Taluk are willing to use them for their banking operations.
- The percentage mean shows that 81.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 3.42 ± 0.5379) respondents strongly opine that Core banking channels have been useful in different ways and rural students of Mangalore Taluk are willing to use them for their banking operations
- Digital illiteracy is the problem for the success of Core Banking system in rural areas of Managalore taluk. Percentage mean shows that 68.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 2.74 ± 0.664) respondents agree that Digital illiteracy is hindrance for the usage of Core Banking channels in rural parts of Mangalore Taluk.
- Inadequate Digital net work is a problem for Core banking in rural areas. Percentage mean shows that 81.2% (Mean and Standard Deviation $4.0600 \pm .79308$) respondents strongly agree that Digital network is inadequate in rural areas.
- Rural customers have greater fear about safety and security of transactions and about internet fraud. Percentage mean reveals that 87.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 3.5 ± 0.505) respondents strongly agree that rural customers have greater fear about safety and security of transactions and about internet fraud.
- Digital connectivity is not good in rural areas. Percentage mean discloses that 67.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 2.70 ± 0.864) respondents agree that digital connectivity is not good in rural areas.
- Network failure, low speed and delay in conducting the transactions are the major problems in rural areas. Statistical tools obtained for the data collected from the respondents are Percentage mean 76.5%, Mean and Standard deviation 3.06 ± 0.739 . Results clearly indicate that in the opinion of respondents, Network failure, low speed and delay in conducting the transactions are the major problems in rural areas .

REMEDIES AND SUGGESTIONS FOR CBS INCONVENIENCES IN RURAL AREAS:

- Creation of better digital infrastructure is necessary
- Digital education will help to create better awareness among customers
- Creation of digital information cell would help a lot in fulfilling the needs of rural customers
- Creation of Broadband connectivity for all citizens is necessary
- Greater safety must be ensured to customers to preserve the privacy of their transactions

CONCLUSION

Core banking channels play a very important role in digitalizing banking transactions across the country. It is true that there are some rural areas in India, which are lagging behind in infrastructural development. A large number of customers belong to economically weaker sections and they lack computer literacy and are hesitant to use technological devices for their banking transactions. There is a need to create more awareness among customers, particularly among customers of middle age about the latest developments in technology in rural areas. Committee could be set up by the government from Panchayath level in this regard.. Digital education in High Schools should be made compulsory so as to teach students as to how to work with online banking service and how technical issues relating to Core Banking channels can be addressed. Technology when used wisely will definitely produce good results. Core Banking Solutions is not an exemption; CBS software has already marked its own place in the Banking field by making 24X 7days banking possible around the globe.

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PANEL DATA IN TOURISM DEMAND

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Abstract

This study has explained the construction of panel data models, compared the estimation performance of Fixed Effects and Random Effects models in application of tourism demand analysis. Our novelty model of panel data focuses on the 10 best travel destinations according to Tripadvisor award 2018 ($i=1,2,\dots,10$). We have considered the relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for country i (Y_{it}) related to the number of international tourist arrivals in country i (X_1), International tourism receipts for country i (X_2), International tourism expenditures for country i (X_3), Tax revenue in tourism sector for country i (X_4) and Total employment in tourism sector for country i (X_5), for the period 1995 to 2017. After fulfilling all diagnostic tests in panel data and based on the principle of simplicity (Parsimony), we found that the most appropriate model is Fixed Effect model with Individual Effect ($\log Y_{it} = 0.42 \log X_1 + 0.17 \log X_2 + 0.54 \log X_3 - 0.75 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$) where the values of c_i (Unobservable Individual Effects) for each countries such as : Paris (1.776); UK(1.776); Italy(1.839); Indonesia(1.819); Greece(1.736); Spain(1.573); Czech Rep.(1.589); Morocco(1.717); Turkey(1.826) and USA(1.877) respectively. Furthermore, Adj. R-Squared = 0.95054 and F-statistic = 1103.48 (p-value = $2.22e-16 < 0.05$), this implies that the Number of International Tourist Arrivals in country i (X_1), International Tourism Receipts for country i (X_2), International Tourism Expenditures for country i (X_3), and Total Employment in tourism sector for country i (X_5) are adjusted together explain Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for country i (Y_{it}) by 95.054% while the remaining 4.946% is explained by other variables outside the model.

Keywords: Fixed Effects Model; Random Effects Model; Unobservable Individual Effects.

1. INTRODUCTION

The phenomenal growth of both the world-wide tourism industry and academic interest in tourism over the last forty years has generated great interest in tourism demand modelling and forecasting from both business and academic sectors. Lim (1997) noted that, although time series data are widely utilized in estimating tourism demand, few studies use cross-section or

panel data. As an overview, we can see in Romilly et al. (1998) used panel data to develop a model of international tourism spending using both economic and social variables for a total of 138 countries over 7 years. The use of the data panel approach to identify the recent effects of demographic change on Japanese people's travel Propensity is also used by Sakai et al (2000). In the other hand, Ledesma-Rodriguez and Navarro-Ibanez (2001) estimated short-run and long-run elasticities for tourists visiting the Island of Tenerife. In addition, Naude & Saayman (2005) identified factors affecting tourist arrivals to Africa. Garin-Munoz (2006) and Garin-Munoz & Montero-Martin (2007) modeled international tourism demand for the Canary Islands and the Balearic Islands, respectively.

Some other interesting research that uses data panels in tourism demand we can see in Taylor & Ortiz (2009) examined whether climate change has impacted regional tourism in the UK. Brida & Risso (2009) studied the German demand for tourism in South Tyrol using dynamic panel data. Kuo et al. (2009) estimated the impact of Avian Flu on international tourist arrivals to Asian, European and African countries and Habibi et al. (2009) developed a panel data model of international tourism demand for Malaysia.

Hsiao (2003) and Baltagi (2013) lists several benefits of using panel data analysis, these include the following:

1. The use of panel data enables us to control for individual heterogeneity, Panels data Bring more sufficient informative data, then it impacts to be more variability, less collinearity among the variables, so that it comes to be more degrees of freedom and more effective and efficient
2. With the Panel data, one is better able to study the dynamics of adjustment.
3. The Panel data are more suitable for identifying and measuring effects that are simply not detectable in pure cross-section or pure time-series data.
4. The Panel data models allow us to construct and test a more complicated behavioral model than do pure cross-section or time-series data.
5. Micro panel data gathered on individuals, firms, and households can be measured more accurately than similar variables measured at the macro level. Biases resulting from aggregation over firms or individuals may be reduced or eliminated.
6. Macro panel data, on the other hand, have longer time series and, panel unit root tests have standard asymptotic distributions and do not suffer from the problem of nonstandard distributions encountered with unit root tests in time series analysis.

Panel data are most useful when we suspect that the outcome variable depends on explanatory variables that are not observable but correlated with the observed explanatory variables. Parameter estimation in regression analysis with cross-section data carried out with OLS estimation. This method will give the results of the estimation which is the Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE) if all of the Gauss Markov assumptions are met including non-autocorrelation. When we are dealing with panel data, this last condition is certainly difficult to fulfill so that parameter estimation is no longer for BLUE. If panel data is analyzed by approaching time series models, then there is information on the variety of unit cross-sections

that are ignored in modeling. One of the advantages of panel data analysis is considering the variety that occurs in unit cross-sections. The purpose of this study is to explain the parameter estimation of the panel data model with the approach of Fixed Effects Model and Random Effects Model, to find out the best model in panel data parameter estimation and to analyze the best model in panel data parameter estimates using diagnostic test criteria. This study has explained proportionally the construction and estimation of Panel data models in an application to tourism demand analysis.

2. METHODOLOGY

Panel data are also known as cross-sectional time series data or longitudinal time series data is a dataset in which the behavior of entities is observed across time. These entities could be countries, individuals, companies, states, etc. In general, there are three-panel models that are often used, namely pooled regression model, the fixed-effects model and the random-effects model.

2.1 Pooled Regression Model

The equation for the Pooled Regression :

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t} \beta_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (i=1,2,\dots,N; t=1,2,\dots,T) \quad (1)$$

Where:

$y_{i,t}$ is the dependent variable where i represents countries and t represents time. The i subscript, therefore, denotes the cross-section dimension, whereas t denotes the time-series dimension; $x'_{i,t}$ is vector of k -variables independent from entity- i and observed in the t -time period (i.e., there are k independent variables, where each variable is panel data); $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is the error term, The error term is identical and independently distributed or iid $(0, \sigma_{\varepsilon}^2)$ for all i and t . Estimates for this model can be done using the usual OLS (Ordinary least square) method. For the panel data model, it is often assumed that the effect of changes in X is assumed to be constant in time and cross-times category.

2.2 Fixed Effects Model

The pooled regression model can be rewritten, and then given additional constants components c_i and d_i

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t} \beta_{i,t} + c_i + d_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (i = 1,2,\dots,N; t = 1,2,\dots,T) \quad (2)$$

Where,

c_i denotes the unobservable individual effect; d_i denotes the unobservable time effect. When contain c_i and d_i , is called a two-way fixed effect model, whereas if $d_i = 0$ or $c_i = 0$ called a one-way fixed effect model. If the number of observations is the same for all cross-time categories, the model is balanced and if on the contrary, it is imbalanced. For the one-way fixed effect model, it is often assumed that the component $d_i = 0$, which is owned by the model.

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t} \beta_{i,t} + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{3}$$

2.3 Random Effects Model

We can see the effects of various characteristics that are constant in time or constant between individuals by using random effect models. Random effect models are generally written as follows

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t} \beta_{i,t} + w_{i,t} \tag{4}$$

Where :

$$w_{i,t} = c_i + d_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{5} \text{ With}$$

$c_i \sim \text{IID}(0, \sigma_c^2), d_i \sim \text{IID}(0, \sigma_d^2)$ and $w_{i,t} \sim \text{IID}(0, \sigma_w^2)$ independent of each other

If component of d_i or c_i is assumed to be 0, it is called a model The One-Way Random Effect Model, whereas in other circumstances it is called The Two-Way Random Effect Model.

2.4. Generalized Least Squares

We can write $W_i = [w_{i1}, w_{i2}, \dots, w_{iT}]$ In view of this form of w_{it} , we have what is often called an “error components model” then, for this model,

$$E[w_{it}^2] = \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \sigma_u^2,$$

$$E[w_{it} w_{is}] = \sigma_u^2, t \neq s.$$

For the T observations for unit i, let $\Omega = E[w_i w_i']$. Then

$$\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \dots & \sigma_u^2 \\ \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \dots & \sigma_u^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \dots & \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \sigma_u^2 \end{bmatrix} = \sigma_\varepsilon^2 I_T + \sigma_u^2 i_T i_T' \tag{6}$$

Where I is a T x1 column vector of 1s. Since observations I and j are independent, the disturbance covariance matrix for the full nT observations is

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} \Omega & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \Omega & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \Omega \end{bmatrix} = \Omega \otimes I_n \quad (7)$$

This matrix has a particularly simple structure.

For generalized least squares, we require $V^{-\frac{1}{2}} = I \otimes \Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ therefore, we need only find $\Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, which is $\Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \left[I - \frac{\theta}{T} ii' \right]$ Where $\theta = 1 - \frac{\sigma_\varepsilon}{\sqrt{T\sigma_u^2 + \sigma_\varepsilon^2}}$ the transformations of y_i and X_i for

GLS is therefore

$$\Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}} y_i = \frac{1}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \begin{bmatrix} y_{i1} - \theta \bar{y}_i \\ y_{i2} - \theta \bar{y}_i \\ \vdots \\ y_{iT} - \theta \bar{y}_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

And likewise for the rows of X_i . For the data set as a whole, generalized least squares is computed by the regression on these partial deviations of y_{it} on the same transformation of x_{it} . Note the similarity of this procedure to the computation in the LSDV model, which has $\theta = 1$. It can be shown that the GLS estimator is, like the OLS estimator, a matrix weighted average of the within and between units estimators:

$$\hat{\beta} = \hat{F}^W b^W + (I - \hat{F}^W) b^b \quad (9)$$

Where

$$\hat{F}^W = [S_{xx}^W + \lambda S_{xx}^b]^{-1} S_{xx}^W$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\sigma_\varepsilon^2}{\sigma_\varepsilon^2 + T\sigma_u^2} = (1 - \theta)^2$$

2.5. General Feasible Generalized Least Squares Models

The estimated error covariance matrix is $\hat{V} = I_n \otimes \hat{\Omega}$, with

$$\hat{\Omega} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\hat{u}_{it} \hat{u}_{it}^T}{n} \quad (10)$$

the error or mismatched covariance structure inside every group (if Effect= "Individual") of observations to be fully unrestricted may be affected by this framework. Then, it against any

kind of intragroup heterokedasticity and serial correlation. This structure is identified identically across groups and that general FGLS is inefficient under group wise heterokedasticity and Cross-sectional correlation is does not include a priori. Furthermore, the number of variance parameters to be estimated with $N = n \times T$ data points is $\frac{T(T+1)}{2}$, which makes these estimators particularly suited for situations where $n \gg T$.

2.6 Model Analysis

2.6.1 Hausman's Test

We can run a Hausman test to decide between fixed or random effects where the null hypothesis is that the preferred model is random effects vs. the alternative the fixed effects. It basically tests whether the unique errors (ui) are correlated with the regression, the null hypothesis is they are not. Hausman (1978) developed a test based on the idea that under the hypothesis of no correlation, both OLS in the LSDV model and GLS are consistent, but OLS is inefficient, whereas under the alternative, OLS is consistent, but GLS is not. Therefore, under the null hypothesis, the two estimates should not differ systematically, and a test can be based on the difference. The other essential ingredient for the test is the covariance matrix of the difference vector, $[b - \hat{\beta}]$:

$$Var[b - \hat{\beta}] = Var[b] + Var[\hat{\beta}] - Cov[b, \hat{\beta}] - Cov[b, \hat{\beta}] \quad (11)$$

Hausman's essential result is that the covariance of an efficient estimator with its difference from an inefficient estimator is zero, which implies that

$$Cov[(b - \hat{\beta}), \hat{\beta}] = Cov[b, \hat{\beta}] - Var[\hat{\beta}] = 0 \text{ or that } Cov[b, \hat{\beta}] = Var[\hat{\beta}]$$

Inserting this result in (16) produces the required covariance matrix for the test,

$$Var[b - \hat{\beta}] = Var[b] - Var[\hat{\beta}] = \Sigma \quad (12)$$

The chi-squared test is based on the Wald criterion:

$$W = \chi^2[K] = [b - \hat{\beta}] \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} [b - \hat{\beta}] \quad (13)$$

For $\hat{\Sigma}$, we use the estimated covariance matrices of the slope estimator, in the LSDV model and the estimated covariance matrix in the random effect model, excluding the constant term. Under the null hypothesis, W is asymptotically distributed as chi-squared with K degrees of freedom (Greene, W.H, 2003).

2.6.2 Breusch and Pagan's Test

This test aims to see whether there are individual/time (or both) effects in the data panel, namely by testing the hypothesis in the form

$H_0 : c_i = 0, d_i = 0$, or there is no a two-way effect (individual effect and time effect)

$H_0 : c_i = 0$, or there is no individual effect

$H_0 : d_i = 0$, or there is no time effect

We look at a Lagrange Multiplier test developed by Breusch and Pagan (1980), the test statistics is given by

$$LM = \frac{NT}{2(T-1)} \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N e_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T e_{it}^2} \right) - 1 \right]^2 \quad (14)$$

Where e_{it} denotes the OLS residual on the pooled model, e_i denote their sum over t , respectively. Under the null hypothesis H_0 this LM statistics is distributed as a χ_1^2 .

2.6.3. Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge Test

Under the null of no serial correlation in the errors, the residual of a model must be negatively serially correlated, with $cor(\hat{\varepsilon}_{it}, \hat{\varepsilon}_{is}) = -\frac{1}{(T-1)}$ for each t, s . Wooldridge suggests basing a test for this null hypothesis on a pooled regression of FE residuals on themselves, lagged one period:

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_{i,t} = \alpha + \delta \hat{\varepsilon}_{i,t-1} + \eta_{i,t} \quad (15)$$

Rejecting the restriction $\delta = -\frac{1}{(T-1)}$ makes us conclude against the original null of no serial correlation.

2.6.4. Pesaran CD Test

Pesaran (2004) recommended a simple test of error cross-section dependence (CD) that is applicable to variety of panel models, including stationary and unit root dynamic heterogeneous panels with small T and Large N . The proposed test is based on an average of pairwise correlation coefficients of OLS residuals from the individual regressions in the panel rather than their squares as in the Breusch-Pagan LM test:

$$CD = \sqrt{\frac{2T}{N(N-1)}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \sqrt{T_{ij}} \hat{\rho}_{ij} \right) \quad (16)$$

Where
$$\hat{\rho}_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T e_{it}e_{jt}}{\left(\sum_{t=1}^T (e_{it}^2)\right)^{1/2} \left(\sum_{t=1}^T e_{jt}^2\right)^{1/2}},$$

$\hat{\rho}_{ij}$ is the product-moment correlation coefficient of a model's residuals; e_{it} denoting the OLS residuals based on T observations for each $i=1,\dots,N$. In the case of an unbalanced panel only pairwise complete observations are considered, and $T_{ij} = \min(T_i, T_j)$ with T_i being the number of observations for individual I; else, if the panel is balanced, $T_{ij} = T$ for each i, j . Under the null hypothesis of cross-section in dependence, $CD \sim N(0,1)$.

2.6.5. Robust Covariance Matrix Estimation.

Wald-type tests is used for Robust estimators of the covariance matrix of coefficients, consistent vs. serial correlation is generally resulted in the context of panel data version. Basically, all types assume there is no correlation between errors of different groups while allowing for heteroskedasticity. All types assume no correlation between errors of different groups while allowing for heteroskedasticity but no serial correlation, i.e.

$$\Omega_i = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{i1}^2 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{i2}^2 & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & \sigma_{iT}^2 \end{bmatrix} \tag{17}$$

While “White2” is “White1” limited to a common variance inside every group, estimated as $\sigma_i^2 = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{\hat{u}_{it}^2}{T}$ so that $\Omega_i = I_T \otimes \sigma_i^2$, lets a totally general structure w.r.t heteroskedasticity and serial correlation

$$\Omega_i = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{i1}^2 & \sigma_{i1,i2} & \dots & \sigma_{i1,iT} \\ 0 & \sigma_{i2}^2 & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \sigma_{iT-1,iT} \\ \sigma_{iT,i1} & \dots & \sigma_{iT,iT-1} & \sigma_{iT}^2 \end{bmatrix} \tag{18}$$

The latter is, as already observed, consistent w.r.t timewise correlation of the errors, but on the converse, unlike the White 1 and 2 methods, it relies on large n asymptotics with small T.

3. An Empirical Study in Panel data approach

3.1. Novelty of the Model

Panel data methods we can use when both time series and cross-sectional data are available and when only the relationship between the tourism demand variable and its determinants is of interest. We are interested in examining the relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) are related to the Number of international Tourist Arrivals, International Tourism Receipts, International Tourism Expenditures, Tax Revenue in tourism sector, and Total Employment in Tourism sector.

TripAdvisor, the leading travel review site, has ranked the world's best travel destinations of 2018. The site's Travelers' Choice Awards for destinations recognised travellers' favourite destinations around the world. According to TripAdvisor award 2018, the 10 Best Travel Destinations in 2018: 1).Paris, France; 2).London, United Kingdom; 3) Rome, Italy; 4) Bali, Indonesia; 5).Crete, Greece; 6).Barcelona, Spain; 7).Prague, Czech republic; 8)Marrakech, Morocco; 9) Istanbul,Turkey; 10)New York City, USA. This is novelty model in tourism demand focus on the 10 best travel destinations of 2018 and data are compiled from <https://data.worldbank.org>, for the period 1995 to 2017.

After transformation original data used natural log, the panel model represent as:

$$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Where the variable definitions for country i are:

Y_{it} = Gross Domestic Product (US\$) for country i;

X_1 = Number of International Tourist Arrivals (number of person) for country i;

X_2 = International Tourism Receipts (US\$) for country i;

X_3 = International Tourism Expenditures (current US\$) for country i;

X_4 = Tax Revenue in tourism sector (%) for country i;

X_5 = Total Employment in tourism sector (%) for country i;

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ = Slope coefficient for $X_1 \dots X_5$;

c_i = the unobservable individual effects;

d_t = the unobservable time effects;

ε_{it} = the usual disturbance term which varies across regions and time;

$i = 1, 2, \dots, 10$ (the 10 Best Travel Destinations in 2018);

$t=1,2,\dots,230$ (from 1995- 2017).

R-studio software is used for panel model analysis. To describe the calculation of the panel model where the panel model will be estimated is presented as follows:

Model I :

$$\log Y_{i,t} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model II:

$$\log Y_{i,t} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model III:

$$\log Y_{i,t} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

3.2. Analysis Model

3.2.1. Hausmann Test

In this study we used transformation model with natural log, and then for analysis model, first of all we consider to used Hausmann Test for data.

Table 1. Hausmann Test for Fixed versus Random Effects Model

Model	Statistics Test	p-value	Conclusion
Model I	6.2911	0.2789	Fixed Effects
Model II	12.958	0.01148	Random Effects
Model III	4.0757	0.3959	Fixed Effects

Source : Data Processed

H_0 : Fixed Effects model is used for Panel Model

H_1 : Random Effects modes is used for Panel Model

The Hausman Test helps us to decide between the fixed effects and Randon effects or to select the model will be used for analysis. In this case, if the p-value >0.05 then use Fixed effects, if not use random effects.

3.2.2. Breusch-Pagan Test

Summary results of Breusch-Pagan Test is given in the following table 2,

Table 2 Summary results of Breusch-Pagan Test

Model	Hypotesis	Statistics test	<i>p-value</i>	Conclusion
Model I	$H_0 : c_i = 0, d_i = 0$	286.51	< 2.2e-16	H_0 rejected, there is a two-way effect
	$H_0 : c_i = 0$	283.01	< 2.2e-16	H_0 rejected, there is a individual effect
	$H_0 : d_i = 0$	3.4932	0.06162	H_0 is accepted, there is no time effect
Model II	$H_0 : c_i = 0, d_i = 0$	147.29	< 2.2e-16	H_0 rejected, there is a two-way effect
	$H_0 : c_i = 0$	142.98	< 2.2e-16	H_0 rejected, there is a individual effect
	$H_0 : d_i = 0$	4.3057	0.03799	H_0 rejected, there is a time effect
Model III	$H_0 : c_i = 0, d_i = 0$	427.54	< 2.2e-16	H_0 rejected, there is a two-way effect
	$H_0 : c_i = 0$	422.13	< 2.2e-16	H_0 rejected, there is a individual effect
	$H_0 : d_i = 0$	5.4077	0.02005	H_0 is accepted, there is no time effect

Source : data processed

From the results of the hausman and Breusch-Pagan test above, it can be concluded that the models will be estimated are presented as follows:

Model I : Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect,

$$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model II: Random Effect Model with two-way effect (Individual effect and time effect)

$$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model III: Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect

$$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

3.3. Model Estimation

Model estimation can be done using the Generalized Least Squares in Fixed-Effects Model and Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) in Random- Effects Model. To specify the models and type of effect from the panel analyzed we have used Rstudio

software. Finally, model I is reduced to the best panel model, namely *Model A (Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect)*: $\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$; model II is reduced to the best panel model, namely *Model B (Random Effect Model with Individual effect and time effect)*: $\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$, and model III is reduced to the best panel model, namely *Model C (Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect)*: $\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$

3.4. Diagnostic Tests

For the best panel models that have been reduced (Model A, model B, and Model C) diagnostic tests have been conducted following:

3.4.1. Testing for Serial Correlation

Serial correlation tests apply to macro panels with long time series. Not a problem in micro panels (with very few years). The null is that there is no serial correlation. In this study we used Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge test for serial correlation in panel model where

H_0 : There is no serial correlation

H_1 : There is serial correlation

Summary results of Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge test for serial correlation in panel models is given in the following table 3:

Table 3. Summary results of Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge test for serial correlation

Model panel	Statistics test	p-Value	Conclusion
Model A	0.51537	0.7728	There is no serial Correlation
Model B	1.7725	0.4122	There is no serial Correlation
Model C	0.7699	0.6805	There is no serial Correlation

Source: data processed

Interpretation for model A: ‘p-value < 0.7728, accepted H_0 , there is no serial correlation; Interpretation for model B: ‘p-value < 0.4122, accepted H_0 , there is no serial correlation; and Interpretation for model C: ‘p-value < 0.6805, accepted H_0 , there is no serial correlation.

3.4.2. Testing for cross-sectional dependence/contemporaneous correlation

The null hypothesis in Pasaran CD tests of independence is that residuals across entities are not correlated or connected. The residuals are tested by Pasaran CD (cross-sectional dependence) and it will be correlated across entities*. Cross-sectional dependence can lead to bias in tests results (also called contemporaneous correlation)

H_0 : There is no cross -sectional dependence

H_1 : There is cross -sectional dependence

Summary results of Pasaran CD test for Cross-sectional dependence in panel models is given in the following table 4:

Table 4. Summary results of Pasaran CD test

Model panel	Statistics test	p-Value	Conclusion
Model A	0.13552	0.8922	There is no Cross-sectional dependence
Model B	-1.359	0.1741	There is no Cross-sectional dependence
Model C	-3.2423	0.001186	There is Cross-sectional dependence

Source: data processed

It can be seen that the model C does not fulfill the assumption that there is a Cross-sectional dependence in the model so that it is excluded from the best possible model for the panel model.

3.4.3. Testing for Heteroskedasticity

Robust Covariance Matrix Estimation can be used for testing heteroskedasticity. We can see that standard errors given different types of HC (Heteroscedsticity), we found that there is no heteroskedasticity in Fixed Effects model and Random Effects Model, is given in the following table 5 and table 6.

Table 5. Controlling for Heteroskedasticity :Fixed Effects

	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_4
0	195791	7264911	6443014	8419023
1	206327	7328920	6499781	8493201
2	215598	7366955	6550383	0.08550706
3	235913	7471906	6660124	8685710
4	241640	7497062	6673373	0.08739503

Source: data processed

Table 6. Controlling for Heteroskedasticity :Random Effects

	(Intercept)	β_1	β_3
C0	927842	8013458	6492875
C1	953712	8066236	6535638
C2	965705	8097449	6557599
C3	1004054	8182568	6623206
C4	995587	8173095	6613156

Source: data processed

4. Estimation Results

It can be seen from the overall results of the analysis above, that models A and B were obtained that met the results of the diagnostic test. To determine which model is best presented through table 7 below

Table 7. Fixed effects and Random Effects models : Estimation results

MODEL A (Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect):				
$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	Pr(> t)
β_1	0.419731	0.093715	4.4788	1.216e-05 ***
β_2	0.171607	0.071369	2.4045	0.01704 *
β_3	0.543294	0.041771	13.0064	< 2.2e-16 ***
β_5	-0.747976	0.078490	-9.5295	< 2.2e-16 ***
Total Sum of Squares				50.856
Residual Sum of Squares				2.3726
R-Squared				0.95335
Adj. R-Squared				0.95054
F-statistic				1103.48
p-value				< 2.22e-16
MODEL B (Random Effect Model with two-way effect/Individual effect and time effect)				
$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.833420	0.225393	3.6976	0.0002176 ***
β_1	0.479763	0.047238	10.1564	< 2.2e-16 ***
β_3	0.606135	0.038210	15.8633	< 2.2e-16 ***
Total Sum of Squares				54.835
Residual Sum of Squares				3.5669
R-Squared				0.93495

Adj. R-Squared	0.93438
Chisq	3262.73
p-value	< 2.22e-16

Source: data processed

By looking at the value of the Residual Sum of Squares (RSS) of each model, where for models A=2.3726 and model B=3.5669, based on the principle of simplicity (Parsimony) that by viewing the minimum of RSS value. It can be concluded that model A is the best model. We can see also, the value of Adj. R-Squared for model A =0.95054 higher than the value of Adj. R-Squared for model B=0.93438. We found that model A: $\log Y_{it} = 0.42 \log X_1 + 0.17 \log X_2 + 0.54 \log X_3 - 0.75 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$ (The fixed effect model with individual effects) is the best panel model, with values of the unobservable individual effect (C_i) for each country presented in table 7.

Table 7: Ci Value for each Country, the 10 Best Travel Destinations 2018

Countries	France	UK	Italy	Indonesia	Greece	Spain	Czech rep.	Morocco	Turkey	USA
C_i	1.776	1.776	1.839	1.819	1.736	1.573	1.589	1.717	1.826	1.877

Source: data processed

In table 5 we can see for the best model in panel data is model A (Fixed Effects Model with Individual effect), where β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are all significant (t-value > Pr(>|t|)), this implies that the positive effect on Gross Domestic Product (GDP) arising from Number of International tourist arrivals (X_1); International Tourism Receipts (X_2); and International Tourism Expenditures (X_3), although the negative effect on Gross Domestic Product (Y_{it}) arising from Total Employment in tourism sector (X_5), where β_5 is also significant (t-value < Pr(>|t|)) Furthermore, Adj. R-Squared = 0.95054 and F-statistic = 1103.48 (p-value = < 2.22e-16), this implies that all independent variables are adjusted together explain the variable GDP (dependent variable) by 95,054% while the remaining 4.946% is explained by other variables outside the model and all independent variables are statistically significant at a = 5% which means all independent variables have a significant influence on the GDP variable.

5. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Based on the F test, the Number of International Tourist Arrivals, International Tourism Receipts, International Tourism Expenditures, and Total Employment in the tourism sector, have a simultaneous significant influence to The Gross domestic product (GDP). Results of this study shows that the International Tourist Arrivals, International Tourism Receipts, International Tourism Expenditures, and Total Employment in tourism sectors as factors that can explain changes in Domestic Products Gross (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA.
- 2) Based on t-test, the number of International Tourist Arrivals has a partial positive impact that is significant to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Results of this study reveal that the

- Number of International Tourist Arrivals as a factor that can explain changes in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA.
- 3) Based on t-test, International Tourism Receipts has a partial positive impact that is significant to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Results of this study show that International Tourism Receipts as a factor that can explain changes in The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA.
 - 4) Based on t-test, International Tourism Expenditures has a partial positive impact that is significant to the Gross domestic Product (GDP). Results of this study show that International Tourism Expenditures as a factor that can explain changes in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA.
 - 5) Based on t-test, Total Employment in the tourism sector has a partial negative impact that is significant to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Results of this study show that Total Employment in the tourism sector as a factor that can explain changes in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA. Its surprising results that may reveal the possibility of unreported transactions, low payment to increased employment and the black market in the sector that does not reflect the reality of employment contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP).
 - 6) Based on Adj.R square, this implies that the Number Of International Tourist Arrivals, International Tourism Receipts, International Tourism Expenditures, and Total Employment in the tourism sector, adjusted together explain the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by 95.054% from Paris, UK, Italy , Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA while the remaining 4.946% is explained by other variables outside the model.

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SUSTAINABLE TOURISM SUPPLY CHAIN AND ICT ROLE IN SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION HOSIPITALITY.

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Tourism supply chain involves package in several services: 1. Travel agencies operators' e-tourism, to finalize tourism. 2. Finalize tourism package, transport, and accommodation, hotel industry which includes catering, food beverage, leisure services, sports activities, and health services. The co-operation of network inside supply chain can represent a competitive advantage to small tour operators, wherein are more sensitive to competition, in tourism supply chain. The correlation between tourism, and sustainability, of tourism industry is the attraction, competition of each of the organization with tourism industry in supply chain. Tourism is multi-segment industry, where products are consumed on the spot. Tourism industry is also fragmented industry, with high complexity, due to price sensitiveness nature, of demand and the perishability, intangibility, in the tourism industry in supply chain. Tourism like all other business in supply chain operates through B2B relationship, and can delivery, sustainability performance improvement through good financial performance of the tourism industry, by working to improve the business operation of each supplier in supply chain. The difference in tourism supply chain is that tourist are in demand, with the product demand, and the product they procure, which are of high service requirement in higher proportion , and which requires prompt or immediate production to enjoy the holiday preference. The most important distribution system applied in tourism supply chain; 1. One stage: from a primary supplier of services to a consumer through reservation, either directly to travelers. 2. Two stage: where the system involves any middle man or an agent to do the work. In tourism industry distribution strategy has an impact on development, and it is essential to channel the distribution in an appropriate form from the beginning to end to end in supply chain tourism.

Concept of tourism in supply chain: Tourism supply chain industry comprises of suppliers, operators, tourists and other organizations, and tourism supply chain, purchasing various resources, and they transferring them to services, and support which finally goes into the hands of the tourists.

Supply chain tourism is also determined by comprehensive products travel industry in supply chain which necessarily cannot supply all the services required in coordination with relevant tourism aspects in supply chain.

Features: Supply chain as compared to traditional manufacturing industry, supply chain tourism is characterized by high complexities, risk, and very important is the quality control aspect in supply chain tourism, complexity of the tourism products, also leading to complexity of the tourism leading to complicated process in supply chain tourism.

The requirement of high quality coordination allocation, and a reasonable resource allocation, and if uncontrollable a good quality of service may not be admissible in catering, accommodation, good transportation, supplier efficiency, which are the aspects that face challenges, and it is necessary for the travel enterprises to coordinate any semi-finished product, necessary for tourist in supply chain, and control product quality.

Problems faced by supply chain in tourism: Tourism is basically to satisfy the needs of the tourist, either domestic or internationally, however the allocation of the needs is to be optimized. Tourism do lack any special innovation in supply chain, which is caused by intensive market competition, in the field of supply chain. Any depth of tourism experimental ideas, and supplies pertaining a high class content, becomes insufficient.

Tourism in supply chain has also given preference to individual travelers, with relevant information on arranging of trips, having made through Internet of Things facilities.

Based on supply chain tourism many scenic spots have come back on competitive terms, and this way of marketing, and reception centre, has made e-commerce to get in touch with tourists in supply chain, with reference to accommodation, catering, and entertainment.

In this junction many travel enterprises are gradually losing their positions of their potential in the market, hence a diversified tourism supply chain has been adopted to personalize tourists in supply chain.

In the tourism supply chain travel enterprises are provided with risk which are complicated, as they are unable to respond to the market changes in tourism supply chain, and this has led to changes in supply chain, and this consequences has led to short term benefits, thus ignoring the scenic spots, which result in damages to environment, and that have no influence in tourist in supply chain.

In order to bring in sustainable tourism in supply chain, is that planning should be developed to manage tourism activities from a perspective point, in the long run, and on the other hand reduce the damaged caused to tourism, on travelling, like maintaining the ecological balance of tourism, industry, and protection, development of tourist sports, in supply chain, in order to improve the quality and economy of the country in supply chain.

Tourism in supply chain should have the responsibility to protect culture, environment scene, water sports activities, and medical programs, thus reduce damage to environment, and chose low carbon transportation, E-commerce tourism.

Platform to develop mobile App, which has changed the way to obtain information, and delivery, results in supply chain. Tourism development in supply chain has realized the time and space, limitation, and traveler can deal with suppliers and other information directly. Tourism development in supply chain is collectively analyzing travel information that should be beneficial to make quick decision, and improve products and services.

Green Tourism in Supply chain: Supply chain is given prominence and priority in the development of green tourism, and requires to examine, and evaluate various manufacturing organization to make, and source to disposal that can be coordinated, and controlled as green supply chain, in the design, manufacturing, maintenance, marketing, and consumption of products in tourism supply chain.

Inventory strategy in supply chain tourism: The most important strategy is the inventory classification that attracts tourism is the activities that coincide with accommodation, transportation, that are necessary to match with an understanding or visitors demand, satisfaction, destination, and ensure that the expectations are met.

Customer service strategy in supply chain tourism: providing accommodation, flight details, and a attraction of tourist destination, which are an vital part of the tourism industry in supply chain.

Customer satisfaction integration: supply chain integration that links all the entities in supply chain preferably manufacturing, suppliers, distribution, customers, cooperation, to form a supply chain, and develop products into a single organization with greater integration process in tourism supply chain.

Sustainable in tourism business can also develop the existing business in tourism, and attract view in business, opportunity in supply chain, and increase the revenue in supply chain, as it also contributes to the reputation of the organization operating the supply chain. The supply chain that contribute with quality to improve, and to provide better customer service, with contribution to increase customer satisfaction, strength, bring in value enhance publicity, and marketing tourism opportunities and have better acceptance in supply chain.

Sustainable supply chain management is the trend to use the policies of purchase, and the practices to facilitate sustainable development at the tourist destination. Research on environmental aspects of manufacturing, while other aspects of sustainability, or the challenges for service sector are largely ignored, but sustainable supply chain has given to the important tour operators, as the product depends on the activities of suppliers, such as providing accommodation, transportation, and relevant activities that form an important part of the contribution to a sustainable tourism, which will be more effective through responsibility for the which the impact of the supplier is important in supply chain.

Supply chain comprises the suppliers of all the goods and services, that go into the delivery of tourism, which the products to the consumer, but also to maintain the harmony among the different aspects, which affects largely the satisfaction of the tourist in the tourism industry. If the tourists become satisfied and contented, they will come again, and it is liable to increase the revenue, which can be distributed, so the prime concern of the tourism and supply chain is necessarily satisfied with guests being given importance, and thus earn profit.

Main parties involved in supply chain are the providers of accommodation, transporters, and the activities handlers in their day to day functions in tourism, which involves also the food supply, and the operations of supply which operates in B2B relationship, and that the supply chain is able to deliver a sustainable performances, along with the financial planning performances by working on improved business, so that each supplier benefits by the life cycle.

The main difference between tourism supply chain and other sectors is that tourist travels to the product, and the product they buy have a particular high performance and service, as it involves the higher proportion of people involvement, in the production for which a holiday experience at a sustainable supply chain is envisaged. Tourism management is a sustainable management and cannot be diminished.

Tourism and hospitality industry are mainly developed, influenced by the size of information, and the digital technology usage in an environment. The growth of information and communication technology has become an integral part of the hospitality industry. The use and spread of information and communication technology has brought in a great potential to accelerate growth in tourism and hospitality, and in the process human resources has been developed, by reducing the regulatory network in the development of tourism and hospitality industry, thus increasing the knowledge.

Information and communication technology offers good innovative ideas to cities embedded around with good buildings; good water management systems, excellent road/rail transportation (metro rail) developed in big cities, efficiency in energy system (solar/wind/thermal) power, and thus reduce waste management.

Information and communication technology innovation application offers good transport, manufacturing, agriculture, urban development, which help to bring in the climate change, and it optimizes value chain, in supply chain, by reduction in cost, resource usage, and emissions, thus providing resilience to climate adaption, with launching of space programs, bringing in real timely climate and weather information.

Information and communication technology, manages crisis management, disruption, and has the means of implementing of a consumption pattern by the use of data, which increases transparency, and which empowers the economic development.

Information and communication technology, implements good partnership in most global manufacturing industries promoting technology, building capacity in production, improving hospitality, by enabling data build up and having accountability to the cost.

Sustainable development is so much in focus on the global warming and climate change, and also continuous depletion of natural resources. Implementation of sustainable consumption and production pattern is going on to achieve a sustainable development in tourism and hospitality industries. The growth of industrialization is making developing countries more susceptible to unsustainable pattern of production and consumption.

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